

The Evolution of Main Sequence Galaxies from $z \sim 0-6$

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Abstract

Using a compilation of 20 papers published since 2007, we investigate the evolution of the star-forming galaxy (SFG) Main Sequence (MS) out to $z \sim 6$ (age ~ 0.9 Gyr). These data encompass star formation rate (SFR) indicators from 1.4 GHz–UV, many MS galaxy selection methods, and both direct-detection and stacked data. After converting all observations to a common Kroupa initial mass function (IMF), we find a remarkable consensus among MS observations across all SFR indicators, which further improves once biases from selection methods are accounted for. We fit robust functional forms for the MS as a function of time using the observed mass ranges in each sample to account for evolving MS mass distributions and observational limits, and find that in all cases the MS slope is not constant in time. Using these fits, we are able to deconvolve the observed scatter about the MS within the observed redshift bins. After accounting for scatter between different SFR indicators, we find the width of the distribution may be as small as $\sim .2$ dex and remains constant over time, consistent with the scatter we observe between publications. We use empirical evolutionary tracks in order to constrain galaxy star formation histories, and show that scatter in the MS can easily be generated via differential evolutionary tracks.

1. Introduction

Large advances in both theory and observation have substantially increased our knowledge of the distant and the local universe in the last decade. Wide-field and deep multi-wavelength surveys have allowed us to study statistically large samples of galaxies at a wide range of redshifts in unprecedented detail. Advances in stellar population synthesis (SPS) modelling (Fioc & Rocca-Volmerange 1997; Bruzual & Charlot 2003; Maraston 2005; Percival et al. 2009; Conroy et al. 2009; Conroy & Gunn 2010) and improved global diagnostics of galactic star formation (Murphy et al. 2011; Hao et al. 2011; Kennicutt & Evans 2012 (KE12), and references within) have enabled

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the determination of key physical quantities of galaxies from these data: photometric redshifts, star formation rates (SFRs; ψ), stellar masses (SMs; M_*), dust attenuation (usually measured by $E(B - V)$ or A_V), and stellar ages (Benítez 2000; Bolzonella et al. 2000; Feldmann et al. 2006; Collister et al. 2007; Brammer et al. 2008; Ilbert et al. 2009; Abdalla et al. 2011; Acquaviva et al. 2011; Johnson et al. 2013; Moustakas et al. 2013).

These new advances have allowed us to determine accurate rest frame colors for many of these objects, and indicate that galaxies out to high redshifts seem to fall into two distinct groups in color space: “star-forming” and “quiescent” (Labbé et al. 2005; Wuyts et al. 2007; Williams et al. 2009; Ilbert et al. 2010; Brammer et al. 2011; Ilbert et al. 2013). New studies of physical quantities have revealed key differences between these groups, and have revealed a strong correlation at fixed redshifts between M_* and ψ among SFGs, which takes the form

$$\log \psi = \alpha \times \log M_* + \beta, \quad (1)$$

or, alternately,

$$\psi = e^\gamma \times (M_*)^\alpha, \quad (2)$$

with $\gamma \equiv \ln 10 \times \beta$, and α and β are free parameters of the fit. α is usually measured to be between 0 and 1 (Chen et al. 2009; Elbaz et al. 2011; Lee et al. 2011), with values of $\sim 0.6-1$ preferred (Rodighiero et al. 2011), and both α (MS slope, i.e. power-law index) and β (MS normalization) are likely to be functions of time $\alpha(t)$ and $\beta(t)$. This relationship has been shown to hold for over 4–5 orders of magnitude in mass (Santini et al. 2009) and from $z = 0$ to $z \sim 6$ (Brinchmann et al. 2004; Salim et al. 2007; Noeske et al. 2007; Elbaz et al. 2007; Oliver et al. 2010; Daddi et al. 2007; Rodighiero et al. 2011; Whitaker et al. 2012; Wuyts et al. 2011b; Karim et al. 2011; Zahid et al. 2012; Santini et al. 2009; Lee et al. 2012; Speagle et al. 2013). This relation is quite tight, with only $\sim 0.25-0.35$ dex of scatter (Daddi et al. 2007; Whitaker et al. 2012).

On average, galaxies on this star-forming galaxy (SFG) Main Sequence (MS) formed stars at much higher rates in the distant universe than they do today: at fixed M_* , the average ψ has decreased at a steady rate by a factor of ~ 30 from $z \sim 2$ to $z = 0$ (Daddi et al. 2007; Elbaz et al. 2007). Furthermore, this MS forms an increasing proportion of the galaxies observed at earlier times, indicating an evolving relationship between MS and quiescent galaxies (Brammer et al. 2011; Ilbert et al. 2013). This has been linked to the rapid quenching of star formation (Bell et al. 2007) and downsizing paradigm (i.e. more massive objects seem to evolve more quickly) for galaxy evolution (Barger et al. 2005).

Although there have been a host of studies of the MS in the past decade, quantitative comparisons between them have been difficult as studies have not standardized their calibrations and methodology. Differences in assumed IMF, $L-\psi$ conversions, SPS models, and emission line contributions can lead to differences in derived SMs and SFRs as high as a factor of 2–3 (KE12; Karim et al. 2011, as compared to KE12; Magdis et al. 2010; Stark et al. 2013). Differences in assumed cosmology even can lead to offsets of up to 10% (such as the differences between the cosmology from Kashino et al. 2013 and the one assumed here; see Table 4).

Many of these effects have not yet been systematically corrected for, mainly because the prevailing assumption has been that the intrinsic variation between different SFR indicators and within the MS itself would not make direct comparisons very useful. While these concerns are legitimate, this lack of consensus makes it difficult to determine actual MS evolution, especially if both the slope *and* normalization of the MS are changing over time. For instance, while some studies have found significant evolution in MS slope as high as $\alpha(z) = 0.70 - 0.13z$ from $z \sim 0-2.5$ (Whitaker et al. 2012), others seem to indicate little to no evolution over the same redshift range (Karim et al. 2011). Furthermore, the variation *between* MS slopes from various studies at a given redshift is also significant, reaching as high as ~ 0.6 (Elbaz et al. 2007; Oliver et al. 2010), twice as large as the evolution observed by Whitaker et al. (2012) since $z \sim 2.5$. As the slope and normalization are highly degenerate, samples that have similar overall M_* and ψ distributions but have been selected differently can have large differences in their MS fits, leading to changes in the derived slopes by up to ~ 0.4 (Karim et al. 2011; Whitaker et al. 2012). The magnitude of these effects preclude robust interpretations of derived MS properties.

The inability to directly compare observations has also made it difficult to quantify how the scatter about the MS has evolved. While observations out to $z \sim 2.5$ find scatter to be roughly constant around ~ 0.3 dex (Noeske et al. 2007; Santini et al. 2009; Whitaker et al. 2012), the scatter observed at each median redshift is convolved with evolution of the MS within its redshift bin, as well as with additional scatter resulting from uncertainties in ψ and M_* (Noeske et al. 2007). Salmi et al. (2012) attempt to account for this effect by simultaneously fitting power-law corrections as a function of redshift to their derived MS fits. This method, however, is not robust, as it only provides information for how the MS evolves across the redshift bin in question, and furthermore is dependent on what functional form is chosen to implement the correction. So the evolution of the intrinsic, “true” scatter about the MS has not yet been thoroughly investigated.

In order to overcome these limitations, inter-publication comparisons have by and large used average SFRs (either across the whole sample or at a specific mass) after simple IMF corrections to determine the approximate evolution of the average MS galaxy’s SFR, rather than the derived MS’s themselves (Magdis et al. 2010; Zahid et al. 2012). This method has been useful in estimating the evolution of the cosmic (i.e. per cubic Mpc) SFH (cSFH) to first order, and has done much to explain the cosmic SFR density evolution observed in Hopkins & Beacom (2006). However, it averages over the observed $M_* - \psi$ relations, and so does not take into account much of the information surrounding the mass dependencies that govern the MS.

In order to directly compare MS observations against each other and so constrain MS evolution and systematic errors, we have compiled $\psi(M_*, z)$ from 20 studies published since 2007, spanning $z \sim 0-6$, taken from a variety of fields, selected using different methodologies, with SFRs determined from all methods currently available, including both direct stacked and direct-detection (DD) data, and converted them to the same absolute calibrations. By taking into account the differing mass ranges in each study considered, we not only accurately determine MS evolution, but also quantify the extent to which selection can affect observed MS determinations. These results allow us to

determine the evolution of both the MS and the “true” scatter about it as a function of time.

In § 2 we discuss some of the technicalities surrounding observations of the MS and how we deal with them when converting MS observations to a common metric. In § 3, we describe the data included in this work. In § 4, we describe our mass-dependent method of fitting this inter-publication dataset. Our results are listed in § 5; our best fit is $\alpha(t) = (.74 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03) - (.032 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.003) \times t$ and $\beta(t) = (5.53 \pm 0.2 \pm 0.28)(0.04 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03) \times t$, where the errors listed are from the formal errors on the fit and from bootstrapping, respectively, and t is the age of the Universe in Gyr. We discuss implications of these results, such as galaxy evolutionary tracks derived using Main Sequence Integration (MSI), in § 6.

Throughout this work, we standardize to a $(H_0, \Omega_m, \Omega_\Lambda) = (70, 0.3, 0.7)$ WMAP concordance cosmology (Spergel et al. 2003), AB magnitudes (Oke & Gunn 1983), a Kroupa & Weidner (2003) [KW03] IMF, integrated from 0.1–100 M_\odot , KE12 $L-\psi$ relations, and Bruzual & Charlot (2003) [BC03] SPS models.

2. Calibrating the Main Sequence

Differences in the assumptions and techniques used to derive the MS can lead to major offsets in the final derived MS relations. Here, we split effects up based on their possible total influence on elements involved in deriving the MS, categorized into large ($\gtrsim 25\%$) and small ($\lesssim 25\%$) effects, respectively, and discuss their effects and how we can correct for them. Finally, we discuss the effects of differing selection methods that are outlined in Table 1 and how they influence the overall distribution of the MS relation. For a more in-depth review of many of the points discussed below, see KE12, ?, Kroupa et al. (2013), and Conroy (2013).

We denote all correction factors to the MS relation outlined in this section with the form C_j , where j denotes the particular attribute being corrected for, and C is in units of dex. The calibrations that we choose to apply are listed in Table 2, and the corresponding correction factors that are applied to each sample are listed in Table 4.

2.1. Large Influences

2.1.1. Initial Mass Function

In order to utilize SPS modelling, an stellar IMF¹ must be assumed in order to determine the proportion of stars that contribute to UV and optical continuum, the key components used to constrain SFRs and SMs, respectively.

Currently, there are several IMFs that are often used to derive MS properties. The most prominent are those of Salpeter (1955), Chabrier (2003), and Kroupa (2001), most commonly integrated from $0.1 - 100 M_{\odot}$, which will be referred to as Salpeter, Chabrier, and Kroupa IMFs, respectively. The assumed IMF approximately equally impacts both the derived SMs and SFRs, leading to variations of up to $\sim 40\%$ (KE12). However, there currently is no consensus in the literature on the appropriate conversion factor necessary to convert from one IMF to another (Elbaz et al. 2007; Salim et al. 2007; Chen et al. 2009; Papovich et al. 2011; Zahid et al. 2012). Given this, we choose to implement IMF corrections taken from Zahid et al. (2012)² in order to apply a self-consistent set of IMF conversions. These take the form

$$M_{*,K} = (1.06)M_{*,C} = (.62)M_{*,S}, \quad (3)$$

with the subscripts referring to Kroupa, Chabrier, and Salpeter IMFs, respectively, for SMs derived from (Bruzual & Charlot 2003; BC03) SPS models (see Section). These correspond to SM offsets of $C_{M_*,C} = +0.03$ and $C_{M_*,S} = -0.21$ dex. This agrees well with the SFR corrections from Kennicutt (1998) [K98], which assumes a Salpeter IMF, and those from KE12, which assumes a KW03 IMF, for SFRs derived from the FUV and NUV. In all cases, the shift from a Chabrier to Kroupa IMF is essentially negligible, and only the Salpeter to Kroupa IMF transformation really impacts these data. Although all corrections have been applied for completeness, we note that our results are unchanged if the Chabrier IMF-derived masses are left as is.

This SM adjustment is functionally equivalent to shifting the MS left or right (i.e., increasing/decreasing the SFR at a given mass since all masses are revised downwards/upwards), with the observed mass ranges (see Table 3) adjusted accordingly. This leads to corrections factors in the normalization, C_M , of $-\alpha \times C_{M_*}$. For a slope of unity, these changes merely result in a shift of the observed range of the MS relation rather than the actual MS relation itself. However, as the majority of data compiled here (again, see Table 3) have slopes of *less* than unity, the majority of these changes *do* actually impact the observed normalizations. Their total impact assuming a self-consistent $L - \psi$ relation adjustment, however, frequently is small ($\sim (1 - \alpha) \times C_{M_*}$).

¹Usually presumed to be universal (i.e. unchanging with respect to time, current and past star formation history, metallicity, etc.). Current evidence seems to imply that this assumption is probably flawed, with the IMF becoming more top-heavy (i.e. forming higher fractions of more massive stars) with increasing SFRs Kroupa et al. (2013); Weidner et al. (2013). Possible ramifications of this for MS evolution are discussed in Davé (2008).

²Also seen in Salim et al. (2007) and Elbaz et al. (2007).

2.1.2. SFR Indicators and the $L-\psi$ Relation

SFRs are calculated based on observed galaxy luminosities in certain wavelength ranges. These most often are the UV continuum from (from $\sim 1500-2500 \text{ \AA}$), $H\alpha$ emission, and the total IR (TIR) continuum (from $\sim 3-1100 \mu\text{m}$). In addition, other SFR indicators, such as 1.4 GHz emission, have further been developed by exploiting the tight observed radio-IR correlation (Yun et al. 2001; Bell 2003), as well as from SED fitting to individual bands (cf. Salmi et al. 2012) or multiband photometry (cf. Moustakas et al. 2013).

Most notably, the studies included here calculate integrated luminosities over the entire wavelength range of interest by fitting specific templates to observed bands. In the IR, these templates most often are taken from Chary & Elbaz (2001) [CE01] and Dale & Helou (2002) [DH02]. In the UV, the most common templates are those from Brammer et al. (2008) [B08] and Brammer et al. (2011) [B11]³. To account for additional strong emission lines, Charlot & Longhetti (2001) [CL01] templates are also sometimes used.

Each of these SFR indicators listed here, whether calculated through direct photometric observations or template fitting, traces ψ in different ways, over different timescales, and with different calibration issues (see Table 1 and Section 3 of KE12), with different $L-\psi$ conversions differing by up to $\sim 50\%$ (see, e.g., the radio SFR calibrations from Yun et al. 2001 and Bell 2003). The standard reference for most calculated SFRs today is K98, which gave SFR calibrations for L_{UV} (1500-2800 \AA), $L_{H\alpha}$, $L_{O[II]}$, and L_{TIR} based on a single power-law Salpeter IMF and a mix of models from the literature (e.g., Madau et al. 1998). While this IMF gave decent SFR calibrations relative to those of more realistic IMFs for indicators such as $H\alpha$, for many of the other wavelengths often studied, the relative calibrations are sensitive to the precise form of the IMF. Today, most astronomers calibrate SFR tracers either using a modern broken 2-part IMF with a turnover below $\sim 1 M_{\odot}$, such as a KW03 IMF, which has a Salpeter slope ($\alpha_* = 2.35$) from $1-100 M_{\odot}$ and much lower $\alpha_* = 1.3$ from $0.1-1 M_{\odot}$, or a Chabrier IMF, which has a log normal distribution from $0.1-1 M_{\odot}$. The calibrations presented in KE12 use this IMF, but, as mentioned in Section 2.1.1, a Chabrier IMF yields nearly identical results (Chomiuk & Povich 2011).

KE12 also takes advantage of major improvements in the last decade surrounding the stellar evolution and atmospheric models used to generate synthetic SEDs, and calibrate their observations using the Starburst99 galaxy models of Leitherer et al. (1999) and Leitherer et al. (2010).⁴ As KE12 provide a *self-consistent* set of $L-\psi$ relations for a more realistic IMF, we opt to convert all previously derived SFRs to this new metric. The ratio of the $\psi-L$ relationships used in individual papers relative to those of K98 and KE12 are listed in Table 1 where applicable, where the latter

³B08 models are technically calculated based on PEGASE.2 and BC03 models, but the scheme by which this is done is non-trivial. See their Section 2 for more info. B11 models are modified B08 models that take into account emission lines.

⁴Frequently updated online, and available at <http://www.stsci.edu/science/starburst99/docs/default.htm>.

column gives the C_ψ numbers listed in Table 4, which include IMF corrections. When SFRs are derived from combinations of IR and UV data, we weight ψ_{UV} and ψ_{IR} according to the average extinction correction from Reddy et al. (2012a) [R12], who find that, on average, $\psi_{UV}/\psi_{IR} = 5.2 \pm 0.6$ in SFGs (see Section 2.1.5).

2.1.3. *Stellar Population Synthesis Model*

In order to derive SMs, SFRs, and other physical parameters, studies need to assume a specific SPS model in order to generate theoretical spectra to use as inputs into their SED fitting procedure. Conceptually, the basic ingredients needed to generate an SPS model are relatively straightforward (Tinsley 1968; Bruzual A. 1983; Moustakas et al. 2013; Conroy 2013). First, a population of stars is generated according to an assumed IMF and metallicity, both taken to be universal and invariant over time (and thus not modelled self-consistently). These are then evolved forward using stellar evolution calculations for stars spanning the full range of initial mass and an assumed star formation history (SFH). At each position in the Hertzsprung-Russell (HR) diagram throughout this process, the spectrum of each star is generated according to pre-existing stellar libraries, and, combined with other assumptions (e.g., abundance pattern, dust mass and grain size distribution, star-dust geometry, and the interstellar radiation field), summed to generate a synthetic spectrum of a galaxy.

Unfortunately, systematic uncertainties in calculating particular phases of stellar evolution, inadequacies in current stellar libraries, and other simplifying assumptions can lead to significant errors.⁵ A prominent example includes the uncertainties in modelling the little-understood evolution of thermally pulsating asymptotic giant branch (TP-AGB) stars, blue stragglers (BS), and horizontal branch (HB) stars, all of which are relatively luminous and can therefore have major impacts on the integrated stellar spectrum (Maraston 2005; Melbourne et al. 2012) ranging from ~ 0.1 – 0.3 dex (25–50%) depending on SPS model (Salimbeni et al. 2009; Conroy et al. 2009; Magdis et al. 2010) in a way that is possibly mass dependent (Salimbeni et al. 2009). SPS calculations also implicitly assume a well-sampled (i.e., fully populated) and unchanging IMF, which may not always be satisfied (Kroupa et al. 2013; see also Section 2.1.1). Although these uncertainties should be taken into account, in practice many of these procedures are difficult to model and computationally expensive, and thus are often neglected (Behroozi et al. 2010).

Multiple SPS models are used in when fitting for SMs and deriving photometric redshifts (photo- z 's). The models used in the compilation presented here are taken from Fioc & Rocca-Volmerange (1997, 1999) [PEGASE.2], Bruzual & Charlot (2003) [BC03], Maraston (2005) [M05],

⁵See, e.g., Conroy et al. (2009), Percival & Salaris (2009), Behroozi et al. (2010), Conroy & Gunn (2010), for recent in-depth discussions on the uncertainties present in existing SPS modelling procedures, and Conroy (2013) for a review of the entire SED modelling process.

Charlot & Bruzual (2007, 2011) [CB07, CB11],⁶ Polletta et al. (2007) [P07], Rowan-Robinson et al. (2008) [R08], and Gruppioni et al. (2010) [G10].⁷ In this study, all SMs (and their corresponding MS corrections) are calibrated as best possible to BC03 models. PEGASE.2 models are assumed to be similar to BC03 since they use similar stellar evolution tracks (i.e. the Padova 1994 stellar evolution tracks),⁸ and so are left as is. RR08 models, although empirically-grounded, are assumed to be similar to BC03 as well since they are regenerated to higher-resolution (and given physical parameters) based upon the SPS models Poggianti et al. (2001), which again use similar stellar evolutionary tracks to BC03. The models of P07 and G10 are fit only in addition to BC03 models in the studies listed here. As the relative rate of their fitting procedure relative to their BC03 counterparts is not detailed in any of the studies provided, they are not corrected for here. The M05, CB07, and CB11 models, however, utilize different prescriptions to treat the TP-AGB phase that substantially differs from the derived BC03 models as detailed above. As the TP-AGB phase tends to dominate much of the starlight at certain wavelengths, the revised prescription tends to revise masses downward. We treat these models as identical because they implement similar TP-AGB prescriptions (Reddy et al. 2012b), and choose to implement a correction upwards of $C_{M*,S} = +0.15$ dex here based on the results of Magdis et al. (2010), which are also an approximate average between the results of Salimbeni et al. (2009) and Conroy et al. (2009).⁹ This gives SPS corrections of $C_S = -\alpha \times C_{M*,S}$.

2.1.4. Star Formation History

As mentioned in Section 2.2.3, different SFHs are needed as inputs to generate the SEDs used to derived galaxy physical properties. The most commonly used of these are declining (D) SFHs, taken from an exponentially-decaying burst with $\psi(t) = \psi_0 e^{-t/\tau}$, where ψ_0 is the SFR at the onset of the burst (and also the scale-factor used in SED fitting procedures), t is the time since the onset of the burst, and τ is SFR e-folding time. D-SFHs are usually modelled with a wide grid of values ranging from tens of Myr to several Gyr (Maraston et al. 2010). Some fitting procedures modify typical D-SFHs by superimposing random starbursts (DRB), usually modelled using a tophat function with a constant SFR and a range of intensities and timescales (Salim et al. 2007; Moustakas et al. 2013; ?).

⁶Although used in the literature, these models have never been officially published.

⁷See <http://www.sedfitting.org>, and Walcher et al. (2011) for extensive references.

⁸Technically, BC03 supplements the Padova 1994 tracks (?????) with tracks from the Padova 2000 library (?) and the Geneva library (??), as well as a couple others (see their Section 2), but for the most part are dominated by the Padova 1994 tracks.

⁹All corrections implemented this way also have the fortunate coincidence of being at similar ages $z \gtrsim 2$, as well as all being selected via Lyman-break criteria (see Section 2.2.4), which lends some additional support to this assumption.

Recent studies, however, motivated by the unphysicality of the extremely short ages usually derived with D-SFHs – plus the implied functional form of the MS for galaxies undergoing significant mass assembly – have advocated *rising* SFHs as better functional fits to the MS than D SFHs. These have taken several forms: that of an exponentially-rising (R) SFHs, with $\psi(t) = \psi_0 e^{t/\tau}$ (Maraston et al. 2010; Gonzalez et al. 2012); power-law-rising (RP) SFHs, with $\psi(t) = \psi_0 t^\alpha$ (Papovich et al. 2011; but also see Smit et al. 2012); and linearly-rising (RL) SFHs, with $\psi(t) = \psi_0 + \frac{d\psi}{dt} t$ Lee et al. (2011). Frequently, constant (C) SFHs are also used as a go-between for the two options, with $\psi(t) = \text{psio}$ Lee et al. (2012).

Given all these current different parametrizations of SFHs,¹⁰ however, it seems that the derived SMs are – assuming BC03 models – largely independent of the chosen SFH assuming reasonable physical constraints on τ (Maraston et al. 2010; Reddy et al. 2012b; ?). The SFRs from R-SFHs/DRB-SFHs in this scenario, by contrast, tend to be ~ 0.3 – 0.4 dex (i.e., around a factor of 2) higher than those from simple D-SFHs (Maraston et al. 2010; ?). However, for τ left free to choose incredibly small values that imply unphysically young ages,¹¹ Maraston et al. (2010) find that the R-SFHs tend to derive SMs of ~ 0.2 – 0.3 dex less than those of D-SFHs, and SFRs ~ 0.5 – 0.6 greater than those of D-SFHs. Given the SFH of a typical MS galaxy, which likely includes both a rising and declining SFH component of varying degrees as a function of observed mass (and hence formation time; see Section 6.2), as well as the small sample sizes of both studies, we defer any possible SFH mass corrections to a later work.

2.1.5. Dust Attenuation

Most studies measure extinction/attenuation by dust using the difference in magnitudes between the B and V bands, $E(B - V)$, either derived through SED fitting (E_S , see below) or observationally (E_O), using the IRX- β relation of Meurer et al. (1999) [M99]. In the literature, E_S values are widely distrusted because of the degeneracies between age and reddening (and hence the assumed metallicity and SFH), and so E_O values tend to be preferred. However, while observational methods such as the IRX- β relation have for a long time been found to give accurate UV-corrected SFRs compared to those derived from UV+IR observations (Bouwens et al. 2012), recent results seem to indicate that this relationship exhibits a significant amount (up to an order of magnitude in some cases) of scatter (Boquien et al. 2012). In addition, results from Wuyts et al. (2011b,a) imply that simple extinction corrections are insufficient to accurately correct for dust, and that more

¹⁰Although not included in this compilation, several studies also include “delayed- τ ” (DT) models, with $\psi = \frac{A}{\tau} t e^{-t/\tau}$, with A a normalization constant and the rest of the variables defined as above (Moustakas et al. 2013). These models allow the construction of D-SFHs ($t/\tau \gg 1$) and RL-SFHs ($t/\tau \ll 1$), as well as several that serve as intermediates between the two.

¹¹(This is an artifact of the “outshining” problem, i.e., that the youngest stars tend to dominate the SED in the UV, where the SFR is best constrained, and thus provide poor constraints on stellar ages without extensive multiband photometry and possibly more complex and physically-motivated SFHs.)

complex geometrical (i.e. patchy) dust models are needed. Regardless, by observing UV versus combined UV and IR (UV+IR) emission from an ensemble of SFGs, R12 are able to derive average “extinction corrections” to convert from the observed UV-derived SFR to the bolometric SFR, with $\psi_{bol} = (5.2 \pm 0.6) \times \psi_{UV}$. As galaxies at higher redshifts ($z \sim 2-7$) seem to exhibit similar dust properties (Schaerer & de Barros 2010; R12), we apply this extinction correction to data which does not correct for it (see Table 4), and also use it weight the corresponding ψ_{UV} and ψ_{IR} components from ψ_{UV+IR} data accordingly when adjusting SFR values using the $L-\psi$ relations from KE12.

2.1.6. Extinction Law

Multiple extinction curves have been used in the literature to account for the effects of dust on the observed SEDs in SPS-generated spectra. The ones used in the papers presented here are taken from Prevot et al. (1984) [P84], from observations of the Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC), Cardelli et al. (1989) [C89], from various sources in the optical and NIR, Calzetti et al. (2000) [C00], from observations of SFGs, Madau (1995) [M95] and Charlot & Fall (2000) [CF00], from observations of nebular attenuation, and Chary & Elbaz (2001) [CE01], from observations of local galaxies. A hybrid C00 model with a bump at 2175 Å [C00b] is also used in some cases (Ilbert et al. 2009). Although the impact of extinction can be as high as a factor of ~ 5 (R12), the impact of using *different* extinction laws seems to be small (Papovich et al. 2001; Dickinson et al. 2003) and will not be corrected for here.

2.1.7. Emission Lines

Strong emission lines, such as Ly α , H α , H β , O[II], and O[III] can significantly alter the SED by contaminating observed band photometry. These lines decrease (i.e. make more luminous) the observed magnitude in a given band by at least 0.1 mag at $z \lesssim 3$; at higher redshifts the contribution is even larger, frequently $\gtrsim 0.2$ mag (Ilbert et al. 2009).¹² These differences, not accounted for (correctly) by most SPS models, can significantly affect the derived physical parameters taken from the SED fitting process and impact the quality of our photo- z 's. Stark et al. (2013) shows the effects that emission line contributions can have on the observed $M_{UV,1500} - M_*$ (i.e. $M_* - \psi$) relationship, and show that while on average the slope of the relation remains the same, the overall fitted masses decreases substantially. We choose to implement corrections from their Figure 7, which lead to SMs to be adjusted by $C_{M_*,E} \sim (-0.05, -0.15, -0.25, -0.4)$ dex for $z \sim (4, 5, 6, 7)$ galaxy samples, respectively.¹³ This leads to MS corrections of $C_E = -\alpha \times C_{M_*,E}$.

¹²See also Figure 3 from the Le PHARE documentation, available at <http://www.cfht.hawaii.edu/~arnouts/LEPHARE/lephare.html>.

¹³We've chosen to apply the correction *without* the hypothesized redshift evolution of the H α equivalent width (EW) based on the results of Finkelstein et al. (2013). If we had taken these into account, the corrections listed above

2.2. Small Influences

2.2.1. Cosmology

The SED fitting procedure to derive a majority of the photo- z 's that we use today are cosmology-independent. Converting these photo- z 's into rest-frame luminosities and SFRs, however, is not, as different cosmologies impact the derived luminosity distances, d_L , at a given z (Hogg 1999). The differing cosmologies used to derive the MS are listed in Table 1. They are corrected for by calculating the ratios between $d_L(z)$ derived from two different cosmologies, and, given the observed redshift range of a sample, calculating the median expected z of galaxies in the sample after weighting for 1st-order volume effects.¹⁴ This is then used to derive the average d_L to MS galaxies in the sample, which are used to correct the derived SFRs ($\propto (d_L)^2$) accordingly. Relative to the possible magnitude of the impacts listed in Section 2.1, this effect is small (< 0.05 dex). All corrections are listed in Table 5.

2.2.2. Photometric Redshifts

For the majority of these galaxies, redshifts have been derived photometrically (photo- z 's) via SED fitting rather than spectroscopically (spec- z 's). SPS models are used to derive these photo- z 's, which simultaneously provide the SMs (and sometimes SFRs) used in these studies. The general procedures for photo- z redshift determination is relatively simple. First, you take a given SPS model, IMF, and a grid of metallicities and evolve the population forward in time according to a grid of prescribed SFHs and given SMs (as described in Section 2.1.4). The final spectra are then modified via possible extinction laws and empirical emission line contributions not reproduced by current SPS models. These series of spectra are then modified according to a grid of redshifts and convolved with a set of prescribed filters. The final SEDs are then fitted to observed photometry, with the best fit chosen providing the object's redshift (as well as the other physical parameters used in the fitting procedure).

These photo- z 's have varying precision, ranging from 0.5%–2% (Ilbert et al. 2013; Whitaker et al. 2012), and can be subject to “catastrophic failures” where the photo- z 's and spec- z 's disagree by more than 15% ($\eta \equiv |z_{phot} - z_{spec}| / (1 + z_{spec}) > 0.15$). Besides just misfits caused by bad photometry, a small number of bands, or a multi-peaked redshift probability distribution function (PDF), this can occur, e.g., by confusing the Lyman break at $\sim 1220 \text{ \AA}$ and the 4000 \AA break (?). Although the errors from the average scatter are small, the effects of these catastrophic failures

would be even larger (e.g., up to an order of magnitude at $z \sim 7$).

¹⁴This volume-weighting assumes an approximately constant number density and slowly changing mass distribution of MS galaxies within the redshift bin in question. The effect is negligible in these cases, only changing the derived d_L corrections by less than a percent, but are more significant when we use it later to deconvolve the scatter about the MS (see Section 4.1).

on the MS relative to that of confirmed spectroscopic samples has yet to be fully investigated. In addition, photo-z’s have not been compared with spec-z’s across the full mass and redshift ranges to which they have been applied, which serve to both check their accuracy and are often necessary for calibration purposes (Abdalla et al. 2011). On the whole, photo-z methods do not seem to induce redshift biases relative to spec-z’s (partially by design), and, as the likely induced scatter is small relative to scatter about the MS and other systematic errors, any possible systematic offsets they have relative to spec-z’s are not corrected for in this study.

2.2.3. SED Fitting Procedure

Besides the variations in generating SEDs that have been detailed above, the SED fitting procedure used to derive photometric redshifts differs for different codes. Codes such as HyperZ (Bolzonella et al. 2000),¹⁵ Le PHARE (Arnouts & Ilbert),¹⁶ EAZY (Brammer et al. 2008),¹⁷ Kcorrect (Blanton & Roweis 2007),¹⁸ ImpZ (Babbedge et al. 2004), and the LRT Libraries of Assef et al. (2008),¹⁹ follow the main SED fitting procedure outlined above (namely that of a template fitting method), and achieve best fits using a standard χ^2 -minimization technique. Other codes, such as BPZ (Benítez 2000),²⁰ ZEBRA (Feldmann et al. 2006),²¹ and iSEDfit (Moustakas et al. 2013)²² implement varying Bayesian/hybrid approaches to the SED fitting procedure. Still others, such as GalMC (Acquaviva et al. 2011),²³ π MC² (Pirzkal et al. 2012), and SATMC (Johnson et al. 2013)²⁴ use Monte Carlo Markov Chains (MCMC) in order to determine best-fit physical parameters and better constrain the underlying posterior parameter distribution. Finally, several photo-z codes such as ANNz (Collister et al. 2007; Abdalla et al. 2011)²⁵ and the SDSS pipeline²⁶ opt out of the standard template-fitting procedure and instead utilize neural networks, deriving a parametrization of

¹⁵<http://webast.ast.obs-mip.fr/hyperz/>

¹⁶Available at www.oamp.fr/people/arnouts/LE_PHARE.html. Also includes options that allow for Bayesian priors, similar to other, more Bayesian-like SED fitting routines.

¹⁷<http://www.astro.yale.edu/eazy/>

¹⁸<http://cosmo.nyu.edu/blanton/kcorrect/>

¹⁹<http://www.astronomy.ohio-state.edu/~rjassef/lrt/>

²⁰<http://acs.pha.jhu.edu/~Lijtxitxo/bpzdoc.html>

²¹www.exp-astro.phys.ethz.ch/ZEBRA

²²<http://www.sos.siena.edu/~jmoustakas/idl.html>

²³<http://www.physics.rutgers.edu/~vacquaviva/web/GalMC.html>

²⁴<http://www.astro.umass.edu/~spjohnson/satmc.html>

²⁵<http://zuserver2.star.ucl.ac.uk/~Lijlahav/annz.html>

²⁶Described at <http://www.sdss.org/dr7/algorithms/photo-z.html>, but not openly available. Also includes a hybrid template-fitting method.

photo- z 's via a training set of multiband photometry and spec- z 's, which they then apply to redshift ranges outside the training sample. Each of these fitting procedures, besides contamination from catastrophic errors, might exhibit biases in the determined photo- z 's relative to the true spec- z 's and/or each other. In order to address this question, Abdalla et al. (2011) compare six different photometric redshift methods, finding that in general, all codes produce reasonable photometric redshift estimates both in both an absolutely and relative sense. Furthermore, they find using a training set (for neural network codes) from a small region of the sky does not seem to produce biases when applied to larger survey areas. MCMC fitting methods also seem to generate photo- z 's and physical parameters consistent with those derived from Bayesian and standard grid-based fitting procedures (Acquaviva et al. 2011; Johnson et al. 2013). Based on these results, we do not opt to attempt to correct for possible differences among SED fitting procedures, and defer such an analysis to a possible future study.

2.2.4. Selection Methods

Selection effects within each study – not to mention within the definition of the MS itself – also can affect both the derived slopes and their evolution as a function of redshift (Karim et al. 2011; Whitaker et al. 2012). Different selection methods are often used, the most common being a simple color-color cut of some sort (Karim et al. 2011; Whitaker et al. 2012; Ilbert et al. 2013). While most of these cuts (see Table 1) are efficient at selecting SFGs, they do not all select the same population. As Karim et al. (2011) shows in their Appendix C, $sBzK$ selection is biased towards more “active” SFGs (i.e. with higher specific SFRs, $sSFRs$, $\phi \equiv \psi/M_*$), excluding good portions of galaxies that are classified as SFGs via other selection mechanisms (there $NUV - r$ vs. $r - J$; $NUVrJ$), and give steeper MS slopes. Whitaker et al. (2012) shows that this effect in addition translates into an inherent bias against redder, more dust-attenuated SFGs (see their Figure 3), which have lower slopes compared to their bluer, less dust-attenuated counterparts.

Because of these effects, selection methods that are inherently biased towards bluer, less dust-attenuated, more active SFG populations (which we will classify as “blue” selection methods) will preferentially select a subset of the MS population with a higher slope relative to other selection mechanisms. These selection methods include $B - z$ vs. $z - K$ ($sBzK$; Daddi et al. 2004a), used from $1.4 < z < 2.5$ (Daddi et al. 2007; Rodighiero et al. 2011; Kashino et al. 2013), the Lyman break (Steidel et al. 1999; Stark et al. 2009; Bouwens et al. 2011), used to select high- z Lyman-break galaxies (LBGs), $U - g$ vs. M_{bol} , or any other cut on the color-magnitude diagram (CMD) that explicitly selects based on blue/red color (Elbaz et al. 2007), and Luminous Infrared Galaxy (LIRG) selection, which . We therefore classify these methods are “blue” selection mechanisms, along with luminous infrared galaxy (LIRG) selected samples (Elbaz et al. 2011).²⁷

²⁷Galaxies with $L_{IR} > 10^{11} L_{\odot}$ are termed luminous infrared galaxies (LIRGs) and are observed to be highly star-forming with large amounts of dust attenuation (E11; also see footnote in E11’s data description). We note that

As can be seen by comparing selection methods from, e.g. Elbaz et al. (2007) (see their Figure 2) and Ilbert et al. (2013) (see their Figure 3), non-“blue” selection methods (which we will term “red” for contrast) seems to provide not only a cleaner cut between SFGs and quiescent galaxies, but a more diverse star-forming population. The total classification scheme of these two selection types are listed in Table 1. As mentioned earlier, while these different selection methods do not seem to affect the average observed SFRs across different publications, they do seem to influence the derived slopes (with bluer selection mechanisms preferring slopes closer to unity and redder selection mechanisms preferring slopes closer to 0.65–0.7) and possibly the intrinsic scatter (with *sBzK* samples uniformly having lower scatter relative to other selection mechanisms; this will be discussed further in Section 6.1).

In Figure 1, we plot the derived slopes of each MS sample color-coded by selection method. As expected, we find that blue-selected MS observations display slopes between $\sim 0.8-1$, while red-selected observations center around $\sim 0.6-0.8$. Based in these results, we decide to use the red/blue classifications to account for different biases inherent in SFG/MS selection. As we tend to prefer a cleaner cut less biased towards active SFGs, we prefer red selection methods as compared to blue ones. Although we will provide fits to all different classifications of data, our best fits will only include the subset of data which have been observed/classified based on red selection methods.

2.2.5. Observational Biases

There are two main biases that characterize observations of the SFG MS: incompleteness and Eddington bias. When a survey is not mass-complete, observations will be biased towards bluer galaxies (similar to the blue selection mechanisms) both due to the nature of most surveys as well as many SED fitting procedures (?), which will affect properties of the MS relation below the mass completeness limit. This is easily rectified by only taking data where the survey is approximately mass complete, as is done in, e.g., Whitaker et al. (2012) (see their Figure 1). For the studies collected here, we find that on average this effect is small, and therefore do not opt to attempt to correct for it here.

Eddington bias (i.e. that random scatter in a given mass/luminosity bin will preferentially scatter objects up into higher mass/luminosity bins because they have comparatively fewer objects), is harder to quantify. An Eddington bias might lead to, for example, a flattening of the MS at high masses as lower SM (and hence lower SFR) objects are scattered up into higher SM bins. This effect, however, should also lead to objects with lower SFRs being upscattered into higher SFR

although LIRGS are definitely SFGs, and thus E11 observed a subset of the SFG MS in the nearby Universe (and see a strong $M_*-\psi$ correlation), they tend to be highly active SFGs with large amounts of dust attenuation and extreme amounts of star formation, in contrast to “regular” MS galaxies that are more similar to the Milky Way at low redshifts from, e.g., Brinchmann et al. (2004) and Salim et al. (2007). LIRGs are thus likely to comprise a very selective subset of MS galaxies, and be biased in the same way as other blue selection methods.

bins (assuming, of course, that the SFR/SM derivations are somewhat independent of one another, as they are constrained by different portions of the SED), causing an upturn in the MS relation. These two effects should then combine to produce a more densely populated upper population in the derived MS relation, with a downturn for samples with well-constrained SFRs and less well-constrained masses (e.g., empirically-derived $H\alpha$ SFRs from high-quality spectra and SED-fitted SMs from high-quality, extensive multiband photometry), an upturn for samples with well constrained masses and poorly constrained SFRs (i.e. empirically-derived UV SFRs, corrected for extinction using the $IRX-\beta$ relation, with SED-fitted SMs from extensive but poor multiband photometry), and a similar slope for samples with about equivalent constraints on both (i.e. both SMs and SFRs derived through SED fitting). In all cases, however, there will be a bias towards higher SM/SFR objects. As these effects should not have a large impact on the derived MS relations (due to the small number of objects at the high mass end), we do not attempt to correct for this effect.²⁸

3. Observations of the Main Sequence

3.1. Selection Criteria

In order to get a robust selection of MS observations, we did a search of papers which met the following criteria:

1. *Includes a published $M_*-\psi$ fit, or else numbers from which such a fit can be derived.* In order to accurately compare MS observations against each other, we require published values of α and β (or analogous quantities). While ample amounts of papers detailing MS evolution have appeared in the last decade, a fair number of these simply detail trends and distributions without providing the parameters of their fits, which are excluded from this study. Note that MS relations derived with sSFRs instead of SFRs have exactly the same parameters as the one we define in Section 1, except with slopes of $\alpha - 1$ (i.e. a slope of unity in $\log M_* - \log \psi$ space is constant in $\log M_* - \log \phi$ space). Our search included all papers with published $M_*-\phi$ relations as well as those with $M_*-\psi$ relations.
2. *The fit(s) need to include more than two data points (if stacked) or 50 galaxies (if directly observed).* This requirement is mainly to avoid biases resulting from small number statistics. For stacked data, two data points do not enable the determination of a χ^2 value to check the goodness of fit and thus possible variance and/or errors, and can be subject to strong variation in galaxies within a certain mass bin either resulting from selection or cosmic variance. For

²⁸For stacked data, which often isn't weighted according to the distribution of objects within each bin, this effect would probably be more prominent. The fact that we don't seem to see signs of Eddington bias in, e.g., MS relations from stacked radio observations from Pannella et al. (2009) and Karim et al. (2011), lends further strength to our assumption that it is in general negligible.

directly observed data, the lower limit of 50 is mainly to avoid fits to very biased sets of data and thus biased MS parameters, such as those seen between Mannucci et al. (2009) and Magdis et al. (2010).

3. *Must include the specifics of their fits, list references where such specifics may be obtained, or else provide data from which such specifics can be easily estimated.* In order to attempt to properly calibrate MS observations against each other, we must know what specific calibrations, detailed in Section 2, were used for each observation. Data for which information such as assumed IMF, SED fitting procedure, $L-\psi$ relation, observed mass ranges, and other parameters listed in Table 1 and 3 are not available were not included in this compilation.
4. *Must have been published no earlier than 2007.* As many papers on the topic have been published, we wish to limit ourselves to more recent observations with larger statistics, better estimates of physical parameters, and improved selection criteria. This is also when the idea of a MS was first proposed by Noeske et al. (2007), and when observations of star-forming galaxies began to become more systematized.

3.2. Data Used

We give brief descriptions of each of the data sets below, although we encourage anyone interested in more details to read the actual paper in question. The main assumptions used to derive the MS relations for each study are summarized in Table 1. MS relations, plus other general information, are listed in Table 3. All studies listed here do not include active galactic nuclei (AGN) in their analysis, removing them via hard X-ray detection matching, SED fitting, and/or power-law fits to observed IR emission.

Chen et al. (2009) [C09]. C09 observes $\sim 10^{5-6}$ and ~ 3000 galaxies in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; York et al. 2000) Data Release Four (DR4; Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2006) and a combination of the Deep Evolutionary Exploratory Probe 2 (DEEP2; Davis et al. 2007) survey and Palomar Observatory Wide Infrared (POWIR) survey at $0.005 < z < 0.22$ and $0.75 < z < 1.0$, respectively. Although C09 do not provide a MS relationship for their fits (which we will term C09(1) and C09(2), respectively) in the paper itself, the fit they *do* provide in their Figure 11 does not seem to include all data points (excluding the ones on the low mass end), and is calculated without assuming extinction. This fit is an outlier from not only other multi-wavelength SFR indicators listed here,²⁹ but also does not utilize an effective cut to exclusively analyze SFGs, in contrast to all the other studies included in this work. We attempt, however, to derive a MS-esque $M_*-\psi$ relation in a self-consistent manner as the rest of the studies listed here as follows. We first take their derived sSFRs for both their SDSS and DEEP2 datasets, listed in Table 2, and correct them for extinction based on the PDFs shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7, in line with other studies. We keep

²⁹It does, however, seem to be consistent with $H\alpha$ SFRs taken from Brinchmann et al. (2004). See their Figure 8.

the $1\text{-}\sigma$ error bars the same, as the shapes of the dust-corrected PDFs are almost identical to those without dust. We fit all the data points with a simple linear fit using total least squares regression with Scipy’s `ODRpack` in order to account for bin size as well as the SFR PDFs. For the resulting $M_*\text{-}\psi$ relationship, we observe that a strong "levelling out" of SFRs at higher masses occurs in both datasets, likely due to increasing amounts of quiescent galaxies included in their mass bins, and therefore opt to exclude the 11–11.5 and 11.5–12 mass bins from the C09(1) sample and the 11.5–12 mass bin from the C09(2) sample. The SFRs are derived by finding the best fit between model Balmer absorption features and the observed features from the composite stacked spectra in each mass bin. SMs are derived for the SDSS sample using the same procedure as described in Brinchmann et al. (2004) [B04] and Salim et al. (2007) assuming a Kroupa IMF. SMs are derived for the DEEP2 sample using the same procedure but assuming a Chabrier IMF, and are corrected to a Kroupa IMF via a conversion factor of 1.12. Extinctions and other parameters are derived via the Balmer decrement and are also detailed in Table 1.

Daddi et al. (2007) [D07]. D07 observe mid-IR (MIR), far-IR (FIR), submillimeter, radio, and UV emission from 1291 *sBzK* galaxies in the Great Observatories Origins Deep Survey (GOODS; Giavalisco et al. 2004) North (GOODS-N; 273 galaxies) and South (GOODS-S; 1018 galaxies) fields from $1.4 < z < 2.5$. Multiband photometry in the optical and NIR is taken from Giavalisco et al. (2004); MIR and FIR from *Spitzer*’s Multiband Imaging Photometer for *Spitzer* (MIPS; Rieke et al. 2004); submillimeter from the Submillimetre Common-User Bolometer Array (SCUBA; Holland et al. 1999) maps of Borys et al. (2003) and Pope et al. (2005); and radio from Very Large Array (VLA) observations taken from an early Morrison et al. 2010 catalog. L_{IR} was derived either by fitting CE01 and DH02 templates or via the radio-IR correlation from Yun et al. (2001), and L_{UV} was derived from K -corrected and extinction corrected B -band flux following Daddi et al. (2004a) [D04]. SFRs are obtained via the $L_{UV}\text{-}\psi$ relationship outlined in D04. Photo- z ’s for GOODS-N were determined by fitting to the empirical templates of Coleman et al. (1980) as described in D04. Photo- z ’s for GOODS-S are taken from Grazian et al. (2006), which uses PEGASE.2 models with D-SFHs assuming a Rana & Basu (1992) IMF (slightly steeper than a Salpeter IMF) and a primordial metallicity. SMs are obtained from Fontana et al. (2004) as detailed in Table 1.

Elbaz et al. (2007) [E07]. E07 use data from two samples – SDSS DR4 ($0.015 < z < 0.1$) and GOODS (both fields; $0.8 < z < 1.2$) – which will be referred to as E07(1) and E07(2), respectively. Both data sets are selected via M_{bol} and $U - g$. E07(1) includes $H\alpha$ emission from 19590 galaxies, and derives SFRs using the B04 calibration, scaling results from a Kroupa to a Salpeter IMF dividing by 0.7. SMs are computed based on Kauffmann et al. (2003) and detailed in Table 1, with results scaled from a Kroupa to a Salpeter IMF as before. Extinctions are derived via the Balmer decrement. E07(2) includes UV emission from ~ 1200 galaxies. Extinctions and SFRs are derived using the calibrations presented in D04, and masses are derived as detailed in Table 1.

Elbaz et al. (2011) [E11]. E11 observe IR emission from 648 LIRGs from the CE01 sample observed with the Infrared Space Observatory (ISO; Kessler et al. 1996), AKARI (Murakami et al.

2007),³⁰ and the Great Observatories All-Sky LIRG Survey (GOALS; Armus et al. 2009) from $0 < z < 0.1$. SMs are derived as in E07. L_{IR} is calculated from $L_{8\mu m}$, and SFRs are calibrated on K98 assuming a Salpeter IMF.

Karim et al. (2011) [K11]. K11 observe 1.4 GHz emission from $> 10^5$ *NUVrJ* galaxies in the COSMOS field from $0.2 < z < 3.0$. SFRs are derived using the calibration from Bell (2003) assuming a Chabrier IMF, which on average gives SFRs a factor of .50 that of KE12 (see Table 1).³¹ Photo-z’s, SMs, and other parameters are derived as detailed in Table 1. In addition to the standard corrections detailed in Section 2, we also apply a $\log(1+z)$ correction, as K11 has overcorrected their SFRs (A. Karim, *private communication waiting on confirmation*).

Kashino et al. (2013) [K13]. K13 observe $H\alpha$ emission from 271 *sBzK* galaxies in the Cosmic Evolution Survey (COSMOS; Scoville et al. 2007) field using the Fiber Multi-Object Spectrograph (FMOS; Kimura et al. 2010) on the Subaru telescope from $1.4 < z < 1.7$. These are selected from the catalog of McCracken et al. (2010), based on deep near-IR imaging ($K_s < 23$) from the Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope (CFHT) and optical imaging (B_J, z^+) from Subaru. SFRs are calibrated on K98 assuming a Salpeter IMF, and extinctions are calculated via the Balmer decrement when available (and averaged by stacking in several mass bins otherwise). Photo-z estimates (and hence SMs) are taken from Ilbert et al. (2009) based on photometry as described in Capak et al. (2007).

Lee et al. (2011) [L11]. L11 observe 1913 LBGs in the NOAO Deep Wide-Field Survey (NDWFS; Jannuzi & Dey 1999) from $3.3 < z < 4.1$. SFRs are derived from the FUV based on the K98 calibration assuming a Salpeter IMF, while masses (and phot-z’s) are derived by fitting a Chabrier IMF as detailed in Table 1. L11 notes that the slope they derive changes from $\alpha = 0.8 - 1$ depending on the assumed extinction parameters, and fit the MS assuming a slope of unity. We, however, take this variation to be intrinsic error on a slope of $\alpha = 0.9 \pm 0.1$, and recalculate the fit with the same normalization scheme, propagating errors accordingly.

Lee et al. (2012) [L12]. L12 observes 2952 and 846 LBGs in the GOODS fields from $3.4 < z < 4.4$ to $4.4 < z < 5.6$, respectively. The relationships presented in L12, however, are in terms of M_{1700} rather than ψ , and do *not* include extinction corrections. To convert M_{1700} to ψ , we take their best fit to the lower- z sample of $\log M = -0.415 \times M_{1700} + 1.2$ (from their equation 13), and

³⁰AKARI data was cross-matched with the Infrared Astronomical Satellite (IRAS; Neugebauer et al. 1984) Faint Sources Catalog ver. 2 (Moshir et al. 1992) and SDSS DR7, and supplemented with data from the AKARI/Far-Infrared Surveyor (FIS; Kawada et al. 2007) all-sky survey Bright Source Catalogue ver 1.0 and photo-z’s from Hwang et al. (2010).

³¹This calibration actually has two components, a linear component for most masses that simply scales with the luminosity, and a luminosity-dependent component for luminosities lower than a characteristic value. For the mass bins K11 use to derive their MS relations (since they wanted mostly "representative" populations – see K11 for more details) this lower mass component is unimportant. We thus choose to focus only on the higher mass component which dominates the fit for all relevant masses.

the best fit to the higher- z sample of $\log M = -0.442 \times M_{1700} + 0.2$, derived by fitting the four median points above the minimum mass presented in Figure 3,³² for the lower and higher redshift bins, respectively, and convert them to luminosities and SFRs using the KE12 relation for the FUV. This gives us the $M_* - \psi$ relations of $\log SFR = .96 \times \log M - 9.02$ and $\log SFR = .90 \times \log M - 7.86$ for the two samples, respectively. As galaxies at high redshift have been shown to have similar dust properties to those at lower redshifts (Schaerer & de Barros 2010), we correct for extinction using R12 corrections.³³ Masses and photo- z 's are derived as detailed in Table 1.

Magdis et al. (2010) [M10]. M10 observes UV emission from 106 LBGs from $2.8 < z < 3.2$, taken from Magdis et al. (2008) and encompassing a variety of fields. SFRs are determined from L_{1500} , using conversions from CB07 models assuming a Chabrier IMF that correspond to ~ 0.54 that of the K98 calibration (see Table 1). SMs are derived using CB07 models assuming a Chabrier IMF, which M10 shows on average are lower than those of BC03 models by a factor of ~ 1.4 . Extinction applied to the SFR is modelled as C00, and derived from the $IRX - \beta$ relation of M99. As M10 provide a slope for their fit ($\sim .91$) but do not provide the normalization, we derive the normalization based on the average mass ($\sim 5 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$) and sSFR ($\sim 4.6 \text{Gyr}^{-1}$) of their sample.

Noeske et al. (2007) [N07]. N07 observes $H\alpha$ (plus various other emission lines calibrated to $H\alpha$), UV, and IR emission from 2905 galaxies in the All-Wavelength Extended Groth Strip International Survey (AEGIS; Davis et al. 2007) with $0.2 < z < 0.7$. L_{IR} (and IR SFRs) were determined following Le Floch et al. (2005) calibrated on Bell et al. (2005), using CE01 templates and a Kroupa IMF, and SFRs were derived via emission lines or corrected UV emission when IR measurements were unavailable. Extinction was calculated based on the Balmer decrement. SMs were obtained from SED fits to optical/NIR photometry by Bundy et al. (2006) and are detailed in Table 1.

Oliver et al. (2010) [O10]. O10 observes FIR emission from $\sim 8 \times 10^5$ galaxies in the Space Infrared Telescope Facility (SIRTF, now *Spitzer*) Wide-Area Infrared Extragalactic Survey (SWIRE; Lonsdale et al. 2003) from $0 < z < 0.8$.³⁴ L_{IR} is derived by fitting a Sc galaxy template from Polletta et al. (2006) to $70 \mu\text{m}$ or $160 \mu\text{m}$ emission. SFRs are then derived via the calibration presented in Rowan-Robinson et al. (2008) via a scaling factor and assuming a given fraction of UV

³²The two highest mass bins are excluded to avoid overweighting the fit and avoid possible Eddington biases. The fit does not change substantially with them included.

³³We check our assumed extinction correction by examining the data from L11, which exhibits an almost identical $\log M = 0.413 \times M_{1700} + 1.367$ relation (see their Figure 3) but which includes a calculated $M_* - \psi$ relation. By equating the relative normalizations of the $z 3.7$ data at $10^{11} M_\odot$, we derive a correction factor of 4.4, which only differs from our assumed R12 factor by $\sim 15\%$ (~ 0.05 dex). We choose to keep the R12 value for consistency with the rest of the papers included here. Note also that the results from Bouwens et al. (2012) seem to imply much lower dust attenuations at these high redshifts, in seeming contradiction with this number and Schaefer & de Barros (2010).

³⁴Observations are given in the paper at higher redshifts but are not included here because they do not fulfill our selection criteria (i.e. they only include 2 points in their fit).

energy is absorbed by the dust. These are higher than K98 SFRs by a factor of 1.13.³⁵ As this assumes a Salpeter IMF integrated from $.15-120 M_{\odot}$ (Babbedge et al. 2004), rather than the usual $0.1-100 M_{\odot}$, we use this offset to convert between the standard Salpeter IMF integration range and the one used here.³⁶ SMs (and photo-z’s) are determined by SED fitting using the templates of Rowan-Robinson et al. (2008), which assumes the same IMF. These templates are empirical, but are regenerated to higher resolution using SPS modelling in order to derive corresponding physical parameters.

Pannella et al. (2009) [P09]. P09 observe 1.4 GHz emission from 11798 *sBzK* galaxies in the COSMOS field from $1.0 < z < 3.0$. SFRs are derived using the calibration from Yun et al. (2001), which is calibrated to the K98 relationship assuming a Salpeter IMF. We find that the SFRs derive differ from those offered in KE12 by a factor of 0.93 (see Table 1), and correct for this accordingly. Masses and phot-z’s are calculated from using the same procedure from D07.

Rodighiero et al. (2011) [R11]. R11 observe UV and IR emission from 19567 and 698 galaxies, respectively, in the COSMOS and GOODS-S fields from $1.5 < z < 2.5$. The UV sample consists of *sBzK* galaxies taken from D07 (GOODS-S) and McCracken et al. (2010) (COSMOS), while the flux-limited IR sample was observed with *Herschel*’s Photodetector Array Camera & Spectrometer (PACS; Poglitsch et al. 2010). Photo-z’s for the *sBzK* sample were taken from Ilbert et al. (2009) and D07 for the COSMOS and GOODS-S fields, respectively, with masses and SFRs have been computed using the same procedure as D07. For the PACS sample, photo-z’s (and SMs) were derived by cross-matching to the catalog of Ilbert et al. (2010) and then fitting via the procedure outlined in Rodighiero et al. (2010a). L_{IR} is derived from PACS fluxes using a P07 and G10 templates as described in Rodighiero et al. (2010b), with SFRs determined from the relationship in D07.

Reddy et al. (2012a) [R12]. R12 observe UV and IR emission from 302 LBGs from $1.5 < z < 2.6$, taken from multiple fields detailed in their Table 1. L_{IR} and L_{UV} are derived from K -corrected fluxes taken from *Spitzer* MIPS 24 μm observations per Reddy et al. (2010) and broadband photometry, respectively. SFRs are derived via combined UV+IR emission assuming a Salpeter IMF calibrated on the K98 relations.³⁷ All objects have spec-z’s. Extinction is derived via the IRX- β

³⁵We would expect this to indeed be higher, since the SFR is assuming some UV contribution, which increases the bolometric SFR at a given IR luminosity. However, by converting back to K98, we can remove the assumed extinction correction and implement the one from R12 for consistency with the rest of the results listed here.

³⁶We note that this is most likely an overcorrection, but only leads to an additional change in MS normalization of $-\alpha \times 0.05$ dex, approximately equivalent to the Chabrier to Kroupa IMF conversion factor assumed here. We fit our MS evolution both with and without this additional correction factor and find that it does not impact our results within the error bars listed in Table 6.

³⁷R12 discuss the effects changing the UV-SFR conversion would have on the subsample of galaxies with very young fitted ages in their Section 4.3 and Appendix A. However, as the majority of their sample consists of older galaxies by design (by imposing restrictions on the SED fitting procedure), this effect should not significantly impact our results.

relation. Masses are determined as per Table 1.

Salim et al. (2007) [S07]. S07 observes 48295 r -selected galaxies from the joint SDSS DR4 and Galaxy Evolution Explorer (GALEX; Martin et al. 2005) data set from $0.005 < z < 0.22$. Although both $H\alpha$ and UV- z -band photometry are observed, the latter is chosen as the superior SFR indicator. The SFR calibration is derived in the paper itself. Masses are taken from B04 and then scaled from a Kroupa to a Chabrier IMF dividing by 1.06. Extinctions and other parameters are listed in Table 1.

Santini et al. (2009) [S09]. S09 observes UV and IR emission from ~ 10000 galaxies in the GOODS MUltiwavelength Southern Infrared Catalog (GOODS-MUSIC; Fontana et al. 2006) from $0.3 < z < 2.5$. SFRs are derived via combined UV+IR emission assuming a Salpeter IMF and scaled based on the calibration in Bell et al. (2005) where IR data is available; otherwise, it is determined via extinction-corrected UV emission derived via SED fitting (which is used to derive the masses and photo- z 's) as detailed in Table 1.³⁸

Salmi et al. (2012) [S12]. S12 observes UV and IR emission from 543 K -band selected galaxies in the GOODS-S field from $0.5 < z < 1.3$, taken from the K -band selected catalogue of D04. The majority of these objects (70%) have spec- z 's; the latter have photo- z 's taken from Grazian et al. (2006). SMs are determined using the method describe in Le Borgne & Rocca-Volmerange (2002) and as used in E07 and E11. L_{IR} is derived using CE01 templates, while L_{1500} is extrapolated from the observed photometry using the best-fitting SED model without extinction, assuming a Chabrier IMF. The extinction is derived by comparing the latter to the total SFR, and used to correct for rest frame colors based on C00. Although there are multiple MS relationships derived in the paper, we only include the one that is most comparable to those from the literature, notably the one with masses derived via SED fitting (rather than their “empirical” mass) that does not take into account color or morphology.

? **[S13].** S13 observe 3424 and 846 galaxies from the flux-limited Spitzer Large Area Survey with Hyper-Suprime Cam (SPLASH; Capak et al. 2012) Epoch 2 data at redshifts $3 < z < 4$ and $4 < z < 6$, respectively. The data is multiwavelength, with observations from the Ultra Deep Survey with the Visible and Infrared Survey Telescope for Astronomy (VISTA) telescope (UltraVISTA; McCracken et al. 2012), *Spitzer*, and Hyper-Suprime-Cam (HSC). Observations so far, however, do not contain HSC data (see SPLASH CITE). Photo- z 's, SMs, luminosities, and extinctions are derived via SED fitting calibrated on K98 but assuming a Chabrier IMF, which are scaled to a Kroupa IMF dividing by 1.06.

Whitaker et al. (2012) [W12]. W12 observe UV and IR emission from 22816 ($U - V$) vs.

³⁸This is further complicated by the fact that S09 employ a $2\text{-}\sigma$ clipped fitting procedure, and many of the SED-derived SFRs tend to be the galaxies that lie outside this range (i.e. quiescent). We attempt to bypass this problem by making assuming that the UV+IR subset of points constitutes a representative population of the MS fit provided, as seems to be the case in their Figure 3, and derive proper UV+IR weights using R12.

($V - J$) (UVJ) selected galaxies from $0 < z < 2.5$ in the NOAO Extremely Wide-Field Infrared Imager (NEWFIRM) Medium-Band Survey (NMBS; Whitaker et al. 2011), which encompasses two fields within COSMOS and AEGIS. L_{IR} is derived based on a single template that is the log average of DH02 templates with $1 < \alpha < 2.5$ following Wuyts et al. (2008), Franx et al. (2008), and Muzzin et al. (2010), while L_{UV} is derived based on best-fitting B11 models. SFRs are derived via the calibration presented in Franx et al. (2008), itself based on the calibration presented in Bell et al. (2005). Photo- z 's are derived using EAZY using PEGASE.2 and M05 templates assuming a Kroupa IMF. SMs are derived using the Fitting and Assessment of Synthetic Templates code (FAST; Kriek et al. 2009).³⁹

Zahid et al. (2012) [Z12]. Z12 use data from three separate metallicity-selected star-forming samples – SDSS DR7 (Abazajian et al. 2009), from $0.04 < z < 0.1$, DEEP2, from $0.75 < z < 0.82$, and the sample from Erb et al. (2006), from $1.41 < z < 2.57$ – which will be referred to as Z12(1), Z12(2), and Z12(3), respectively. Z12(1) includes $H\alpha$ emission from $\sim 2 \times 10^5$ galaxies, and derives SFRs based on Brinchmann et al. (2004) [B04] (with additional improvements given by S07, including aperture corrections), and scale results from a Kroupa to a Chabrier IMF dividing by 1.06. The strong emission lines of each galaxy are fit using the nebular emission models of CL01. Z12(2) includes $H\beta$ emission from 1348 galaxies, with SFRs derived based on K98 (assuming $L_{H\alpha} = 2.86 \times L_{H\beta}$), and scale results from a Salpeter to a Chabrier IMF dividing by 1.7. Z12(3) includes $H\beta$ emission from 87 galaxies, and derives SFRs as Z12(2). For Z12(1), extinctions are determined from the Balmer decrement (assuming a C89 extinction curve). These are then used to parametrize extinction as a function of SM and metallicity, calibrated on Kobulnicky & Kewley (2004), using a similar formulation to Xiao et al. (2012). This parametrization is then applied to Z12(2) and Z12(3) galaxies. Photo- z 's and SMs are derived consistently for all samples, as detailed in Table 1.

In sum, our data is a compilation 20 papers (46 MS relations), as detailed in Tables 1 and 3. 9 (18), 8 (23), and 3 (5) are derived assuming Salpeter, Chabrier, and Kroupa IMFs, respectively. These include ~ 11 different selection mechanisms, 4 (13) classified as “blue” and 7 (33) as “red” (see Section 2.2.4). Of these, 3 (6), 7 (8), 5 (12), 2 (7), 2 (10) studies derive their SFRs based on emission lines, UV, UV+IR, IR, and 1.4 GHz radio observations, respectively. 2 (3) calculate the majority of their SFRs based on SED fitting alone. 15 (27) and 5 (19) studies derive the MS using direct detections versus stacked data. Masses and SFRs are derived using 7 different SPS models, 5 different types of SFHs, 5 different extinction curves – along with 2 independent observational estimates – and metallicities ranging from $0.005 - 2.5 Z_{\odot}$.

³⁹<http://astro.berkeley.edu/~mariska/FAST.html>

4. Fitting the Main Sequence

To fit a robust functional form for the MS that includes not only information on the slope and normalization as a function of time, we want to find a way to incorporate mass information from each MS measurement. In addition, we want to eliminate some of the degeneracies between α and β between samples with similar observational properties (SMs, SFRs, and redshifts) as outlined in Section 2.2.4. In order to do this, we decide to incorporate the observed mass ranges sampled from each study, which are listed in Table 3. These mass ranges have either been taken directly from the paper in question or estimated based on the data included in the relevant fits, rounded to the nearest 0.1 dex. For stacked data, the mass ranges have been taken from the medians of the lower and upper mass bins included in the fit, and thus the errors are approximately equivalent to the width of the bin, or ~ 0.2 dex. When IMF corrections are large (i.e. Salpeter to Kroupa), the reported mass ranges have been adjusted accordingly, again rounded to the nearest 0.1 dex.

Using this additional mass information, we proceed to fit the evolution of the SFR at fixed mass as a function of *time*,

$$\log \psi(t) = a_i t + b_i \quad (4)$$

with SFRs calculated from the reported MS fits in each individual paper, and a_i and b_i are coefficients at a given fixed mass. By fitting a_i and b_i for a grid of masses, we then can derive a function of the form

$$\log \psi(t, \log M_*) = a(\log M_*) \times t + b(\log M_*), \quad (5)$$

assuming a given parametrization for $a(M)$ and $b(M)$. At a given mass, a data point is only included if the MS from the study in question was observed at that given mass. By fitting the evolution of the SFR over time for a given mass, we simultaneously account for the degeneracy between α and β . In other words, instead of fitting the MS by simply averaging over α and β as a function of time, we perform a mass-dependent averaging, picking a subset of the slopes/normalizations at each mass to average over those have been observed. By doing this process for a grid of masses within a specified dynamical range, we then are able to derive a more robust, mass-dependent form of the MS.

In order to eliminate possible outlying MS observations from our data, we decide to remove data in the first and last 2 Gyrs (0–2 Gyr and 11.5–13.5 Gyr) of observations, as determined by the median redshift distributions of the respective samples. We also find that at higher masses, MS observations from C09 and E11 tend to be in serious disagreement with those from the literature, significantly underpredicting and overpredicting the SFR, respectively. As noted in Section 3, both of these are to be expected due to C09’s stacking procedure (which doesn’t effectively cut between quiescent and SFGs) and E11’s highly biased galaxy sample (of nearby LIRGs, which are likely a biased subset of highly active MS galaxies).⁴⁰ Because of their proclivity to skew the distribution, we opt to exclude them from all our MS fits.

⁴⁰Although we exclude them from the fits here, this in no way invalidates E11’s results concerning the impact of galaxy interactions/mergers on upper MS outliers. See also R11 and ?.

As mentioned above, SFRs at a given mass are calculated based on the reported best fit relations from the studies in question. As not all studies report errors on their MS fits, and the errors are symptomatic of the observed scatter about the MS, we instead incorporate errors into our fit by including the *scatter* reported in the papers in question. As the scatter in almost all cases is larger than the reported errors, this process is an extremely conservative estimate that will likely inflate our reported errors. However, as we are fitting observed *SFRs* as a function of time (which display scatter about the best MS fit) in bins of mass, injecting this amount of scatter is actually more physically motivated, which we feel justifies this approach. We plot the $\psi(t)$ relations derived for $\log M_* = 9.5, 10.0,$ and 11.0 in Figures 2, 3, and 4, respectively.

In Figure 5, we plot $\psi(t)$ color-coded by SFR indicator for $\log M_* = 10.5$ (the uncorrected data is plotted in Figure 6, for comparison). As can be seen, while there is good agreement among most selection methods, the red-selected data in general tends to exhibit better agreement than blue-selected data. Because of this, as well as our argument in Section 2.2.4, we opt to exclude blue-selected data when calculating our best fit (although we still include all fits in Table 6). $\psi(t)$ for only red-selected data is shown in Figure 7.

After compiling a_i and b_i values for a grid of masses, we fit them as linear functions of $\log M_*$, with

$$a(M_*) = a_m \log M_* + a_0, \quad (6)$$

$$b(M_*) = b_m \log M_* + b_0, \quad (7)$$

which now gives us

$$\log \psi(t, \log M_*) = (a_{m,t} \log M_* + a_{0,t}) \times t + (b_{m,t} \log M_* + b_{0,t}). \quad (8)$$

Some quick rearranging allows us to write this in a more familiar form,

$$\log \psi(t, \log M_*) = (\alpha_t t + \alpha_c) \times \log M_* + (\beta_t t + \beta_c), \quad (9)$$

where $\alpha(t) = \alpha_t t + \alpha_c$ and $\beta(t) = \beta_t t + \beta_c$ are linear functions of time, and we've redefined $\alpha_t \equiv a_{m,t}$, $\alpha_c \equiv b_{m,t}$, $\beta_t \equiv a_{0,t}$, and $\beta_c \equiv b_{0,t}$ for convenience. In other words, the slopes of both of our fits to $a(M_*)$ and $b(M_*)$ contain information on the slope of the MS, while their normalizations contain information about the normalization of the MS. This leads us to a functional fit to the MS of the form as seen in equation 1, with $\alpha(t)$ and $\beta(t)$ now functions of time. We may also rewrite this new time-dependent equation in terms of a mixed power-exponential (powexp-t) model,

$$\psi(t, M_*) = \psi_{0,t} \times e^{t/\tau} \times M_*^{\alpha(t)}, \quad (10)$$

where $\psi_{0,t} = 10^{\beta_c}$ and $\tau = 1/(\beta_t \ln 10)$. We plot our best fits to $a(M)$ and $b(M)$ for this powexp-t case in Figures 8 and 9, respectively.

Besides a fit as a function of time, we also consider a fit as a function of redshift,

$$\log \psi(\log(1+z), \log M_*) = (a_{m,z} \log M_* + a_0) \times \log(1+z) + (b_m \log M_* + b_0), \quad (11)$$

which is fit in the same way as detailed above for the $\psi(t)$ case. Here, we end up with a slightly different parametrization, with

$$\psi(z, M_*) = \psi_{0,z}(M_*) \times (1+z)^{a(M_*)}, \quad (12)$$

where $\psi_{0,z}(M_*) = 10^{b(M_*)}$. Unlike in the powexp-t case, here we've fit the MS as a mass-dependent power law (pow-z) in z and M_* . On average, values in the literature seem to report that $\psi \propto (1+z)^{\sim 3.5}$ out to $z \sim 2.5$ (R11). As we've fit linear functions for $a(M_*)$ and $b(M_*)$, inputting two fiducial values for $\log M_*$ and doing a simple linear fit gives the predicted MS relation at any given redshift. We plot our best fits to $a(M)$ and $b(M)$ for this pow-z case in Figures 10 and 11, respectively.

4.1. Scatter about the Main Sequence

4.1.1. Deconvolving the Intrinsic Scatter about the Main Sequence

Each MS observation we include has been measured within a predefined redshift window, and therefore has an associated time-window (Δt) that accompanies it. Because of this, the observed scatter about the MS (σ) is actually the real scatter about the MS convolved with the MS's evolution within the given time interval, and thus are overestimates. In order to deconvolve the observed scatter with this effect, we use our best fits to approximate the MS evolution within each time bin, and subtract this evolution from the observed scatter. In order to account for 1st-order volume effects, we assume that within each redshift bin in question, the number density and mass distribution of MS galaxies is approximately constant (to first order), and weight each result according to the changing comoving volume within each redshift bin. Accounting for this effect slightly decreases the total magnitude of the deconvolution (from that of a simple tophat function), and so is again a conservative estimate on the effects of MS evolution within each redshift bin. We then refit the MS using these new, smaller scatters, until we get a convergent solution. We find that differential mass evolution within each time bin is small relative to the absolute changes in SFRs,⁴¹ and approximate the evolution of the MS as one entirely in normalization, with

$$\alpha(t) = \alpha, \quad (13)$$

$$\beta(t) = (-0.15)t, \quad (14)$$

and t once again measured in Gyr. The actual deconvolved scatter (σ_d) in most cases is negligible (see Table 3), but for the data with the largest Δt values the correction leads to a reduction

⁴¹We note, however, that it is *not* negligible, and would imply that there should be a greater evolution at higher masses, and hence more scatter, relative to lower masses. This seems to be in line with hints of increasing scatter at higher masses, as has been hinted at by other studies (Salim et al. 2007). See Section 6.2.

of ~ 0.04 dex. The results are not sensitive to the precise value chosen for $\beta(t)$ here, only the approximate magnitude, with shifts in $\beta(t)$ of ± 0.02 leading to changes in σ_d of at most ~ 0.01 dex.

4.1.2. Calculating the “True” Scatter about the Main Sequence

This deconvolved, “intrinsic” scatter, however, is still not the “true” scatter (σ_t) about the MS. Errors in the actual measurements themselves (i.e. photo-z’s, SMs, and SFRs) will further tend to inflate the observed distribution. In order to account for these observation-induced scatter, we look for metrics by which to estimate the approximate variation present in any given indicator used to derive one of these quantities relative to another, hopefully more reliable, metric.

For observed redshifts, this comparison is easy in principle, as we are able to compare derived photo-z’s against their more accurate spec-z counterparts. As mentioned above, average scatter in the photo-z vs. spec-z relation, ignoring contamination by catastrophic errors, interdependencies on SMs and SFRs, and other observational biases, will tend increase the observed scatter by at most 0.02 dex (for average phot-z vs. spec-z errors of 2%). We will thus not attempt to account for their effects here, and leave a more thorough investigation of their properties to a possible future study.

At the moment, SMs, unfortunately, can only be derived through SED fitting procedures and have no real cross-checks. Although several studies, such as Salmi et al. (2012), have found other indicators that might work as “empirical” SM indicators, any real vetting of such a SM indicator has yet to be undertaken. We are thus not able to account for their effects here.

Although at present no SFR indicator seems to be inherently viewed as “better” than one another, the variety of SFR indicators in use today allows us to use the plethora of cross-checks to attempt to establish some level of intrinsic observational-induced SFR scatter. In order to determine the scatter that might be introduced due to observational techniques, we search for previous instances where cross-calibrations have been established. Using results from N07, ?, S09, ?, Wuyts et al. (2011b), R12, and K13, we find that on average all SFR indicators used today show quite good agreement, albeit with $\sim .3$ dex cross-calibration (σ_{cc}) scatter, irrespective of extinction law, sample size, and SPS model.⁴² Furthermore, σ_{cc} in each case appears to be uncorrelated with both each other and other variables, which holds even for indicators that require extinction corrections such as H α (Wuyts et al. 2011b). This constant scatter does not seem to evolve over a wide redshift range, showing that there doesn’t seem to be possible redshift dependence between the indicators or some evolution of the cross-correlations with time (N07; S09; R12; Wuyts et al. 2011b).

⁴²There is conflicting results concerning SED and UV-corrected SFRs relative to other SFR indicators, with SED/UV-corrected SFRs derived from SED fitting having scatter as high as .5 dex and possible poor correlations compared to other SFR indicators (Wuyts et al. 2011b). Here we will assume that the scatter is similar to the other methods, as has been tentatively confirmed by analysis of SFR indicators in the COSMOS field (Speagle et al., *in prep*).

There are several possible interpretations of this. The first would be that one of the SFR indicators (e.g., $H\alpha$) is intrinsically more reliable than the others (taking the differences in the relative timescales probed into account), and thus should be taken as having very little internal scatter compared to the rest. However, the fact that all indicators seem to share similar σ_{cc} values seems to imply that the intrinsic scatter for most is around equivalent ($\sigma_{int} \sim .2$ dex); otherwise, they should display smaller scatter when being compared with $H\alpha$ versus how much they display relative to each other. This would then imply that the data measured with said SFR indicator should have intrinsically less scatter than those measured via other means, and should be more representative of the population. Ignoring the discrepant *sBzK* small scatters (see Wuyts et al. (2011b) and K13 for discussions on extinction-corrected UV SFRs; see also Section 6.1), we find that on average the $H\alpha$ indicators have less scatter, with $\sigma_d \sim .25$ compared to $\sim .3$ -.35 for other sources.⁴³

Taking this smaller scatter to be emblematic of a smaller intrinsic distribution for $H\alpha$ indicators, we can then assume that $H\alpha$ has an intrinsic scatter (e.g., from internal galaxy properties) that is $\lesssim .2$ dex. We pick fiducial values ranging from $\sigma_{int,H\alpha} \sim 0$ -.15 dex ($\sigma_t \sim 0.2$ –0.25 dex). This implies that the intrinsic scatter among the other observables ranges should range from $\sigma_{int} \sim .25$ –.3 dex, in order to satisfy to $\sigma_{cc} \sim 0.3$ dex. Adding these in quadrature, we get that the *minimum* σ_d must range between .32 and .39 dex. The former (the generous case) is already in tension with several data points, and the latter contradicts most others. Since this is in tension with both the observations listed here and cross-correlation conclusions, we reject this hypothesis. We also construct this same argument for all the other SFR indicators (when possible), and reach similar conclusions. Thus, there does not seem to be one superior SFR indicator which displays smaller internal scatter.

Alternately, we can assume that the observed scatter in each study is almost entirely the result of the scatter among the SFR indicator (i.e. that the SFR indicator scatter is somehow unrelated to the scatter in internal galaxy properties).⁴⁴ This then implies almost perfectly synchronous evolution among objects in a given mass bin, which seems unreal given that range of ages that these studies are covering. Simple differences in formation times due to, e.g., τ , should generate an intrinsic dispersion among SFRs unless evolution was rapidly convergent before/during the era of highest SFR activity ($1 < z < 3$; Hopkins & Beacom 2006) to within $\sim .05$ dex. This would imply that galaxies are synchronous enough to be considered (with proper calibration) standard candles! It would also imply that the processes that trigger and drive star formation are completely deterministic, and dominate at all times over stochastic processes like mergers (at least while galaxies are on the MS).

⁴³However, the fact that these observations, which not only span different times but also differently sized time bins, show similar scatter is concerning, since as noted above there shouldn't be effects like this unless they apply to all bins equally. A casual inspection shows that this isn't true, and that scatters range both relative to t and Δt , in seemingly an uncorrelated way, which tends to rule out this idea.

⁴⁴This would tend to disregard the results of cross-correlational studies entirely, but we ignore this here.

We reject this line of reasoning due to the concerns mentioned earlier in this section, namely that if $\sigma_{cc} \sim 0.3$ dex among all indicators, there must be intrinsic scatter among each indicator, and so this situation cannot be viable.⁴⁵

The most reasonable interpretation it seems would be that the observed $\sim .3$ dex scatter among cross-correlations is in fact due to $\sim .2$ dex of internal scatter individual SFR indicators (also see Section 2 of N07). This can then be easily subtracted in quadrature from the deconvolved scatters to yield approximate "true" scatters (σ_t) in the MS relation. The results are included in Table 3.

We use these new σ_t values in our MS fit, and recalculate σ_d iteratively until our fit converges. The approximation for $\beta(t)$ listed in Section 4.1.1 is the best value after this process.

4.1.3. Success of the Deconvolution Procedure

The success of our fits can easily be seen by examining trends in σ vs. Δt . If we assume an unchanging MS scatter, we would expect that $\sigma(\Delta t)$ should increase for larger time bins due to the increasing effects of MS evolution. After removing the *sBzK* data points, indeed, we find a best fit relation of

$$\sigma(\Delta t) \sim 0.28 + 0.014\Delta t, \quad (15)$$

indicating that, on average, data observed over a larger time range has experienced the effects of more MS evolution. After deconvolution, we find a new best-fit relationship of

$$\sigma_d(\Delta t) \sim 0.28 + 0.005\Delta t. \quad (16)$$

The fact that the relationship maintains approximately the same magnitude, but exhibits a three-fold reduced dependency on Δt , is highly encouraging. We obtain a very similar relationship for σ_t , with

$$\sigma_t(\Delta t) \sim 0.20 + 0.006\Delta t, \quad (17)$$

where the slightly higher evolution is a result of scatter being subtracted in quadrature, which more heavily affects smaller σ_d values. Considering the range of Δt values which this spans ($\Delta t \lesssim 5$ Gyr), these results indicate that the real scatter about the MS is around

$$\sigma_d \sim 0.3 \text{ dex}, \quad (18)$$

and

$$\sigma_t \sim 0.2 \text{ dex}, \quad (19)$$

including likely contributions from SFR indicators.

⁴⁵We could also assume the other extreme, that the scatter among SFR indicators is in fact completely due to internal galaxy properties (e.g., metallicity) that modify the observed emission, rather than the indicators themselves. Cross-correlational studies also seem to rule the extreme version of this hypothesis out, although the results from Salmi et al. (2012) seem to imply that this must be true at least to some extent.

4.2. Cuts

We account for observational biases and other effects by fitting the MS using a variety of cuts in selection mechanism (red or blue), detection type (stacked or direct-detection), SFR indicator (emission lines, UV, UV+IR/IR, radio, SED), and the number of points required per mass bin (ranging from 5–35). Each of these cuts are reported for three sets of data: the uncorrected data, which is listed in Table 3, the corrected data, listed in Table 5, and extrapolated data, which is fit without including any type of mass-weighting scheme (i.e. including all MS observations published for the given cuts and just averaging over their reported α and β). The $1\text{-}\sigma$ uncertainties on the fits are calculated from standard fitting procedures (using Scipy’s `ODRpack`), taking into account the observed true scatter from the observations as well as the interpublication scatter (σ_i). Uncertainties on the fits are also calculated via resampling, where for each trial we randomly adjusting the upper and lower bounds of each observation by ± 0.2 dex (equivalent to the maximum possible errors from stacked data, and a conservative overestimate otherwise), re-fit, and taking the $1\text{-}\sigma$ deviation around the median after 100 runs. We find that our functional form for the MS is robust to possible errors on the reported $\log M$ ranges, and on average generate errors only a factor of only 1–2 higher than the formal uncertainties. Both errors have been listed in Table 6.

5. Results

5.1. The Evolution of the Star-Forming Galaxy Main Sequence

Our results for both our time and redshift fits are listed in Tables 6 and 7. As can be seen both from the interpublication scatter and the errors on the fit, our method is robust both in time and in mass. The small interpublication scatter, in many cases on the order of the true scatter, provides additional support that not only are most MS observations consistent with each other, but that the internal scatter of the MS is less than the standard reported scatter.

As can be seen in Tables 6 and 7, a simple averaging over MS observations while ignoring mass information tends to hide possible differential mass evolution when fitting to all the data, as different selection mechanisms tend to cancel each other out. We find that for the vast majority of the individual data subsets, there is $> 3\text{-}\sigma$ to be evidence for differential mass evolution, sometimes as high as $\alpha_t \sim -0.04$ dex per Gyr and typically $\alpha_t \sim -0.02$ dex per Gyr.

In general, our corrected SFRs show less interpublication scatter, with $\sigma_{i,corr} \sim 0.1\text{--}0.2$ dex in many cases, usually a full ~ 0.05 dex below the uncorrected case. They also display less evolution in $\alpha(t)$: both tend to show similar slopes at $z \sim 0$, but uncorrected data shows steeper slopes (and slightly smaller absolute SFRs) at higher redshifts. In addition, our corrected data does not display bifurcations of the SFR at lower and higher redshift (see Figure 6), and do not have nearly as many outliers (although we exclude those data points from our fit by design since many of them fall within our 2 Gyr edges). Furthermore, given the robustness of our fitting procedure, as visible

from our variation in Tables 6 and 7, we choose to exclude our mass-independent fits.

In all cases, the reason why MS fits change as a function of the minimum number of data points required for the fit, N_{min} , is due to how the decreasing mass ranges allowed for the fits exclude some data at high and low redshifts. Due to downsizing, data at higher redshifts are more likely to contain higher mass galaxies, and thus tend to dominate the fit at higher z . At lower z (i.e. in the nearby Universe), lower mass galaxies tend to be more common due to detection limits that prevent us from observing them at higher redshifts. MS evolution is in fact differential in mass, i.e. at fixed mass, galaxies with larger SMs experience a stronger decline in SFR over time compared to galaxies with smaller SM (see Figures 2, 3, and 4). As the observed amount is not one long continuous linear function (groups of data entering and leaving in mass bins introduce discontinuities; see Figures 8 and 9), excluding the edges tends to decrease the observed amount of differential mass evolution, and hence the extent to which the MS’s mass-dependence (MS slope) evolves over time. Although this slightly alters the change in slopes, the fits compensate by increasing the change in normalization, leading to almost identical MS evolution among these samples over time.

So far, we’ve limited our discussion to our $MS(t)$ fits from Table 6. However, they also hold for our $MS(z)$ fits from Table 7. In order to decide which functional form of the MS provides a superior fit to the data, we turn our attention towards functional robustness, interpublication scatters, and a direct comparison. In terms of robustness, we find that the pow-z functional form is about as robust as the powexp-t one, with both having similar orders of errors and variances. In most cases though, the errors on the pow-z fit are larger than the powexp-t models. For interpublication scatters, we find that on average $\sigma_{i,z} - \sigma_i, t \sim 0.02 - 0.05$ dex. However, we find that it serves as a worse predictor for the MS compared to the powexp-t case.

Based on these criteria, we choose to focus on the odd fits from 35-46 in Table 6, which are for red-selected data only, including all other data types. We take our best MS fit to be that in the middle of the range, with $N_{min} = 10$, where we’ve included enough data points to avoid over-biasing towards individual studies (e.g., S09 at lower mass) but not so much that we eliminate a large portion of the available mass range with which we can use to fit the MS. This gives us our best MS fit as (fit 39)

$$\log \psi(M_*, t) = (.74_{-0.04}^{+.02+.02+.03} - .019_{-0.03}^{+.01+.002+.003} \times t) \log M_* - (5.53_{-.42}^{+.12+.20+.28} - .04_{-.03}^{+.02+.02+.03} \times t) \quad (20)$$

$$\sigma_i = (0.10, 0.12, 0.21) \quad (21)$$

where the first listed errors come from the total variation present in the same sample while varying N_{min} , the second come from formal fitting errors, and the third from resampling variances randomly perturbing the listed mass ranges by ± 0.2 dex. The interpublication variances listed are the minimum, median, and maximum within the fitted mass range ($\log M_* = 9.2 - 11.2$), respectively. This encompasses a majority of the age of the Universe out to $z \sim 2.75$, but provides good fits to

the observed SFRs all the way out $z \sim 5$ (see Figure 7).

6. Discussion

6.1. Scatter and $sBzK$ Selection

We find that the true and deconvolved scatters reported in all $sBzK$ -selected studies (D07, R11, K13) are systematically lower than reported in other papers. Furthermore, their resulting σ_t values are suspiciously low ($\lesssim .1$), with values that seem to imply unphysically low amounts of scatter. This seems to indicate that the scatter observed in these papers is not representative of the redshift range that they encompass, and that $sBzK$ is substantially biased compared to other selection mechanisms.

At first glance, this result seems plausible. Blue selection methods by nature are selecting towards highly-active, non-dusty SFGs; $sBzK$ especially requires a high S/N cut to be effective, further skewing the distribution towards brighter, bluer objects. And with more massive objects on average redder and more extinguished, we would expect that our distribution should be truncated and more tightly correlated than normal. However, this reasoning should apply to all types of blue selection mechanisms, most notably LBG selection. However, data taken from LBGs (e.g., M10, L11, L12, R12) show similar scatters as other red selection mechanisms.

Most likely, this difference is due to an inherent bias built into the $sBzK$ selection mechanism itself. As outlined in D04, the $B - z/z - K$ line used to select BzK galaxies was designed to be parallel to the reddening vector. However, due to the age-extinction degeneracy, this means that age runs perpendicular to the selection function, and implies that you will systematically be missing older (and hence likely more massive and dusty) galaxies because of their redder colors. As LBG selection mechanisms are not explicitly designed this way, although you miss redder SFGs, you do not miss them as systematically as $sBzK$. Thus, while $sBzK$ is effective at selecting out SFGs for $1.4 < z < 2.5$, the distribution and scatter of the sample is biased, with a scatter ~ 0.15 dex (subtracted in quadrature) lower than other samples ($\sigma_{t,BzK} \sim 0.1$ vs. $\sigma_{t,med} \sim 0.2$).

We note that, besides $sBzK$, there is one other data point which displays lower-than-average scatters. One, in the same redshift range as the $sBzK$ studies, is the high- z Z12(3) sample taken from Erb et al. (2006). Most likely, this smaller scatter is due to the small sample size (< 100 objects) and additional metallicity selection criteria. However, we do note that the scatter from the $z \sim 5$ MS observation from S13 is also quite low, at around ~ 0.13 dex. This is likely due to the possible SM–SFR degeneracies and hence reduced MS scatters. We note that smaller scatters would also be predicted in a scenario where scatter about the MS scatter is a measure of the synchronicity of galaxy evolution (i.e. the extent to which galaxies which formed at slightly different times are evolving in sync; Steinhardt & Speagle, in prep; also see Section 6.4). At very early times, the possible spread of galaxy formation times is smaller, and so we would also expect a reduced scatter

in MS observations at higher redshifts. Although this doesn’t explain the higher scatter observed in the L11 and L12 samples relative to the S13 one (which are observed at similar redshifts), it is an intriguing possibility.

6.2. Empirical Main Sequence Evolution Tracks

Using the MS as an empirical constraint, we can formulate evolutionary tracks for the typical MS galaxy with the assumption that they must obey the MS at all times, by simply integrating along the MS. This Main Sequence Integration (MSI; Leitner 2012) method can allow us to get a sense of the typical SFH of a MS galaxy. In figures 15, 16, ??, 17, and 19, we plot the tracks we get for $\log M_*$, $\log \psi$, ψ , and $M_*(t)/M_*(t = t_0)$, respectively, for a typical $\log M_*(t = t_0) = 10$ galaxy assuming a seed mass of $\log M_* = 7$. We include the effects of feedback taken from Leitner & Kravtsov (2011) and Leitner (2012), using their 0th-order and 1st-order approximations. These feedback approximations take into account the SM lost through the death of massive, young stars (0th-order) as well as mass loss from the remaining ensemble of older stars (1st-order); the latter is accurate to within a few percent of the final SM. We assume that galaxies “enter” the MS at a typical SM of $10^7 M_\odot$, as below this stellar mass dwarf galaxies with extremely low metallicities might display significant deviation from typical MS behavior. In addition, galaxies with masses almost this low have been observed at lower redshift (S09), and so this choice is also a good current observational constraint. We note that by assuming such a seed mass we are extrapolating MS evolution to lower masses than is observed at higher redshifts; however, as mass growth is extremely rapid for small masses, the plotted formation times and ages are only weakly a function of mass.⁴⁶

These tracks are particularly insightful in elucidating broad galaxy evolutionary trends. First, we note the two star-forming limits of the MS are clearly present in our tracks. At lower masses, we see that a typical MS galaxy experiences extremely rapid mass growth in a very short amount of time. This amounts to taking the limits $[\alpha(t), \beta(t), \eta(t)] \approx [\alpha, \beta, \eta]$, where $\eta(t_{gal})$ is the SFR–mass growth efficiency as a function of time, which is a function of the age of the galaxy (t_{gal}) and the past SFH. In this limit, the mass growth is simple power law as a function of SM,

$$\frac{dM_*}{dt} \propto M_*^\alpha, \tag{22}$$

and thus

$$M_*(t) = (\alpha - 1) \times (C - t)^{1/(1-\alpha)}. \tag{23}$$

In other words, since $\alpha \lesssim 1$, the MS galaxy is experiencing strong power law (exponential in the $\alpha = 1$ case) growth. This behavior is clearly visible in Figure 15.

At later times, especially in the most realistic case with 1st-order feedback, we can see an approximate linear decline in $\log \psi$. This can be best understood in the slow growth mass limit,

⁴⁶We note that choosing a seed mass of $10^5 (0)$ only adjusts the MS entry time by $\sim 0.25 (0.5)$ Gyr.

where $\log M_*(t) \approx M_*$, and growth is dominated by evolution in α and β . In this case, for a fiducial mass, we end up with

$$\log \psi \sim (\alpha_t \times \log M_* + \beta_t) \times t, \quad (24)$$

which leads to approximately linear decay in $\log \psi$. This behavior is most easily seen in Figure 16.

The strongest argument to include feedback in these cases is most clearly seen in our SFR tracks (Figure 17). Without feedback, galaxies that grow by direct MSI have SFRs that peak at very late times, at $z \lesssim 0.1$. They furthermore only reach low amounts of SFRs, which seem at odds with reported cSFR measurements (Hopkins & Beacom 2006). By incorporating feedback, we not only decrease the time (increase the redshift) where the peak SFR occurs, but also increase its magnitude, as can also be seen in Figure 19. For reference, we also plot $M_*(t)/M_*(t = t_0)$ tracks for a $\log M_*(t = t_0) = 11$ galaxy (Figure ??). Note that for less massive galaxies, more typically seen at lower redshift ($\log M_*(t = t_0) = 10$), the SFR tends to peak around $0.5 < z < 1$ ($8.4 > t > 5.75$; see Figure 19), while for more massive galaxies ($\log M_*(t = t_0) = 11$), the SFR peaks around $z \sim 1$ ($t \sim 5.75$; see Figure ??). These trends are parallel to those seen in mass-differentiated SFR measurements (CITE?).⁴⁷

The sSFR evolution is particularly interesting, as it suggests that MS galaxies become progressively less efficient at forming stars over the course of their lifetime. The sharp drop at earlier times seems to mimic a possible exponential decline (which would drop off as $\sim -t/\tau$), while the levelling out at later times is again reminiscent of the linear decline (i.e. power law) in $\log \psi$. Both of these components are similar to their SM and SFR evolutionary counterparts, as $\log \phi = \log M_* - \log \psi$ is directly related to behavior in both and consequently displays both limits. Here, the effect of feedback on the sSFR can also clearly easily seen, lessening the overall decline in sSFR over time compared to direct MSI tracks. In other words, counterintuitively, it seems that more feedback actually leads to a shallower decline in mass-normalized SFR.

Although our $\log M_*$ track (Figure 15) is useful for seeing the early phases of rapid mass growth, it hides most of the mass growth that occurs at late times. In order to get a sense of the mass growth at larger masses/later times, in Figure 19 we plot the fractional mass growth over time. We can see that, due to the shift to earlier MS entry times, tracks that include better/larger prescriptions of feedback have assembled more mass relative to those that don't at all times. Most notably, we see that MS galaxies are undergoing significant amounts of mass assembly at all times, building up their masses over the majority of the age of the Universe. The fractional mass growth on average is approximately linear with time, minus initial upturns at early times (where rapid mass assembly is taking place) and downturns at late times (where feedback becomes more prominent, especially in the 1st-order case).

⁴⁷This behavior is also very similar to that observed for quasars/AGN in terms of their masses and luminosities (?). This parallel between differential SM/SFR evolution and AGN differential mass/luminosity relation will be further explored in Steinhardt & Speagle (in prep).

6.3. Typical Main Sequence Star Formation Histories

Using these tracks, we are then able to better judge what comprises “typical” MS SFHs, which may help to improve model fits. As mentioned in Section 2.1.4 and listed in Table 1, at the moment a whole range of SFHs are used in SED fitting procedures. As these SFHs might influence SED-derived SFRs by up to several tenths of a dex (Maraston et al. 2010), choosing the proper SFHs for SED fitting is important if we wish to use them to eventually reliably derive more physical properties of SFGs besides just the SM. Our finding can be summarized as follows:

1. At young ages/early times/lower masses, MS galaxy SFHs seem to be well-characterized by a R-SFHs, which can either be modelled as a power-law or an exponential. RL-SFHs do not seem to provide very good fits.
2. At middle ages/times/masses, MS galaxies are forming stars at around their peak SFRs, and instead are most well fit by CSFHs, or by very slowly rising/declining SFHs, depending how far around the peak they are currently being observed.
3. At later times/older ages/higher masses, we see that MS galaxies are best characterized by D-SFHs.

Thus, when fitting a sample of SFGs, one should be using a combination of all three SFHs in order to account for this variation with mass. We find that at no times, except maybe near the peak of the SFR, are MS galaxies well fit by RLSFHs.

We find that no publication to date, with the exception of Moustakas et al. (2013), has fit their galaxies simultaneously with all 3 types of SFHs in order to account for this variation. No publication also has also provided information as to the distributions of their best fit SFHs in either galaxy age or mass. Likely this is because such an increase in parameter space is computationally expensive; however, it is also because, as Maraston et al. (2010) and Reddy et al. (2012b) note, without imposing physical limitations on parameters of the fit, models will tend to pick extremely small τ 's due to the bias towards younger stellar populations. Based on our MSI-derived SFHs, we would expect there to be a changing distribution of SFH with SM, changing from R to C to D SFHs as the fitted mass increases.

Based on these results, we would suggest that the best combination of SFHs to employ would be a through the use DT-SFHs (see Section 2.1.4), where τ is allowed to be both negative and positive to allow for R-SFRs and D-SFHs, which can best simulate many of the SFHs expected on the MS. Furthermore, following recent results from Leitner (2012) and Moustakas et al. (2013) that seem to indicate that the impact of mergers (and hence, of random starbursts) seems to have small/negligible effects on galaxy evolution, we further note that models including random burst components (e.g., DRB-SFHs; ?) will likely not improve fits to the SED, and thus do not need to be included.

6.4. Scatter and Synchronization Timescales

While the tracks discussed above are useful at exploring MS evolution on average, they fail to generate scatter about the observed distribution. Using the 1st-order feedback approximation from Leitner (2012), we explore what varying formation/MS entry times have on the observed distribution at all times. In Figures 21 and ??, we plot the $\log M_*$ and $\log \psi$ evolution, respectively, for MS galaxies that are along the same evolutionary track but have MS entry times (i.e., synchronization timescales) that are offset by ~ 1.4 Gyr. In Figure 23, we then plot the corresponding $M_* - \psi$ relationship for these objects when they are observed at a specific time after the onset of their evolution (in this case, $z = 0.5$). As can be seen, due to both feedback and $\alpha < 1$, galaxies evolving along the same evolutionary tracks at different times display different final $M_* - \psi$ relations, which we show in Figure ?. Furthermore, as can be seen in Figures 25, the true scatter about the MS is a strong function of the synchronization timescales that we pick. And, as Figure ?? shows, is constant over time. Based on the best fit values, we find that completely synchronous evolution (with an offset in “formation” times of ~ 1.4 Gyr) can naturally reproduce the true scatter about the MS.

7. Conclusion

We have compiled 46 MS observations from 20 papers and used them to determine MS evolution out to $z \sim 6$. These data span a wide range of IMFs, selection methods, data type (i.e. stacked or not), redshifts, SFR indicators, and SED fitting assumptions. We then calibrate these data to the same common assumptions, correcting for IMF, $L - \psi$ relation, assumed cosmology, SPS model, extinction, and emission lines. We are able to use these SFRs to quantify the amount of interpublication scatter, which we find is on the order of $\sim 0.15 - 0.2$ dex and at on average ~ 0.05 dex smaller than the uncorrected SFRs. By taking into account mass information, we are able to derive a robust functional form for the MS that indicates strong differential mass evolution, further evidence for downsizing. We derive this MS fit as both a function of redshift and time, and find that the fit where the MS evolves linearly in time provides a better fit than the redshift case. We also observe a strong time-dependent evolution of a possible MS turnoff/turndown/quenching mass, which seems to independently hint at downsizing.

We find that in our MS fits that the different type of selection mechanisms used (i.e. blue or red) in most cases strongly affect the MS slope, with blue mechanisms biased towards higher slopes relative to red ones. Using our best MS relation (excluding blue-selected observations), we are able to deconvolve the observed scatter about the MS with MS evolution within a given redshift bin. After further corrected for SFR-indicator-induced scatter, we find that the likely true scatter about the MS is ~ 0.2 dex, similar to the interpublication scatter. In the same vein, we also find that scatter from *sBzK*-selected samples is systematically smaller than in all other selection methods, including blue ones.

Using these fits, we generate empirical MS evolutionary tracks to constrain the mass growth history and star formation history of typical MS galaxies, and find our results to be in good agreement with observations of both downsizing and cSFR. These tracks also show that scatter about the MS is functionally equivalent to synchronous evolution, with a spread in MS evolution times of ~ 1.4 Gyr. While more observations could be included in this work, including possible MS relations derived from coeval mass/SFR functions, we feel that the current compilation represents a strong constraint on galaxy evolution over the past 12 billion years.

Fig. 1.— The slope of the MS over time, labelled according to their selection type. The clear dichotomy in slope, with blue selected data displaying a relatively constant slope between .8–1 and red selected data showing a time-dependent evolution with slopes trending upwards over time, seems to support our interpretation of our cuts as detailed in § 2.2.4.

JSS thanks Dave Sanders, Martin Elvis and Douglas Finkbeiner for their helpful comments during the editing process, Kevin Bundy, Olivier Ilbert, Brian Feldstein, Daichi Kashino, and Alex Krolewski for helpful discussions, and Rebecca Bleich for all her support.

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Fig. 2.— $\log \psi$ vs. t for $\log M_* = 9.5$, calculated using the best fit MS relations from each study. The data points are labelled as follows: blue squares = UV, purple down triangles = UV+IR, red down triangles = IR, green up triangles = emission lines, yellow diamonds = SED fitting, black circles = radio. The filled points are those directly fitted to the data, while the empty ones are those fitted to stacked data.

Fig. 3.— Like Fig. 2, but for $\log M = 10.0$.

Fig. 4.— Like Fig. 2, but for $\log M = 11.0$.

Fig. 5.— Like Fig. 2, but for $\log M = 10.5$. Here, however, the data are color-coded according to selection method, with blue circles indicating blue selection methods and red squares indicating red selection methods. As can be seen, although the quantitative agreement between both methods is good, the red-selected data seem to be in better agreement with each other.

Fig. 6.— MS data plotted as Figure 2, *before* corrections, for comparison with our corrected data. Bifurcations in the data can be seen at both high and low redshifts, most notably in K11 and O10. The uncorrected data from L12 also are notable outliers.

Fig. 7.— Like Fig. 5, but only including red-selected MS observations and color-coded according in SFR indicator. The agreement when we limit to only red observations is much better than when all data is included.

Fig. 8.— The fitted function for $a(M)$ when we include only red-selected data and restrict the fits to include at least 10 data points per mass bin, and fit the $\psi(t)$ as a function of time.

Fig. 9.— The fitted function for $b(M)$ when we include only red-selected data and restrict the fits to include at least 10 data points per mass bin, and fit the $\psi(t)$ as a function of time.

Fig. 10.— The fitted function for $a(M)$ when we include only red-selected data and restrict the fits to include at least 10 data points per mass bin, and fit the $\psi(z)$ as a function of redshift. As can be seen, the errors are on average higher for the redshift fit than for the time fit.

Fig. 11.— The fitted function for $b(M)$ when we include only red-selected data and restrict the fits to include at least 10 data points per mass bin, and fit the $\psi(z)$ as a function of redshift. Again, errors are on average higher for the redshift fit than for the time fit.

Fig. 12.— The scatter observed for each the subset of the data that was observed directly. The best fit relationships the data are listed in Section 4. The collection of extremely low scatter at higher redshifts are almost exclusively from samples selected using *sBzK*, while the collection of points around $\sim .3$ dex is a rounding artifact, as a large subset of papers report their observed σ rounded to the nearest 0.05–0.1 dex. We see that, as expected, our deconvolution process has the largest effects on data observed in large time bins.

Fig. 13.— True scatter about the MS as a function of time, with red and blue points representative for red and blue selection mechanisms, green points for studies published using *sBzK*, and the magenta point indicating the high- z sample from Z12. The prevalence of *sBzK* point well-below the majority of the data suggests that it is cutting out a significant portion of SFGs.

Fig. 14.— As Figure 13, but for the time spanned by the respective redshift bins (Δt) reported for each MS. Notice the extremely low scatters for *sBzK* points, even though they occupy a relatively small Δt range.

Table 1. Assumptions in MS Derivations

Paper	IMF	SFR indicator	SFR/K98	SFR/KE12	$(t, \Omega_m, \Omega_\Lambda)$	Selection	Red/Blue	SPS Model	SFH	$Z(Z_\odot)$	Extinction curve	Lines? Number
C09	Kroupa	H α /H β	0.48	0.71	(.7, .3, .7)	R/K	Red	BC03	D	0.2-1	CF00	No 2
D07	Salpeter	FUV - 1.4 GHz	0.81	1.29	(.73, .26, .74)	$sBzK$	Blue	BC03	D	0.02-2.5	P84	No 1
E07(1)	Salpeter	H α	0.94	1.38	(.7, .3, .7)	$U - g/M_{bol}$	Blue	BC03	DRB	0.005-2.5	CF00	No 1
E07(2)	Salpeter	FUV	0.81	1.29	(.7, .3, .7)	$U - g/M_{bol}$	Blue	PEGASE.2	? ^a	? ^a	? ^a	No 1
E11	Salpeter	IR	1.00	1.16	(.7, .3, .7)	LIRG	Blue	PEGASE.2	? ^a	? ^a	C00	No 1
K11	Chabrier	1.4 GHz	N/A	0.50	(.7, .3, .7)	$NUVr-J$	Red	BC03	D	? ^a	C00	Yes 9
K13	Salpeter	FUV	1.00	1.59	(.7, .25, .75)	$sBzK$	Blue	BC03/P07	D	1	P84/C00/C00b	Yes 1
L11	Chabrier ^c	FUV	1.00	1.59	(.72, .28, .72)	LBG	Blue	BC03	D/C/RL	1	C00	Yes 1
L12	Chabrier	FUV	.63	1.00	(.72, .28, .72)	LBG	Blue	CB07	D/C	1	C00/M95	No 2
M10	Chabrier	FUV	0.54	0.84	(.7, .3, .7)	LBG	Blue	CB07	D/C	1	C00	No 1
N07	Kroupa	H α /FUV/IR ^d	0.55	0.64 ^d	(.7, .3, .7)	$z < 1.1^e$	Red	BC03	D	? ^a	CE01	No 1
O10	Salpeter	IR	1.13	1.31	(.7, .3, .7)	$36 \mu\text{m}/r$	Red	R08	N/A ^f	? ^a	N/A ^f	No 6
P09	Salpeter	1.4 GHz	N/A	.93	(.7, .3, .7)	$sBzK$	Blue	BC03	D	0.02-2.5	P84	No 1
R11	Salpeter	FUV/IR	0.81	1.29	(.73, .26, .74)	$sBzK/LIR$	Blue/Red	BC03/P07/G10	D	0.02-2.5, 1	P84 ^a	No 1
R12	Salpeter	UV+IR ^b /UV SED	1.00	1.22	(.7, .3, .7)	LBG	Blue	CB11	D/C/R	1	P84/C00	Yes 1
S07	Chabrier	FUV SED/H α	0.77	1.22	(.7, .3, .7)	r_{corr}	Red	BC03	DRB	0.1-2	CF00/M95	No 1
S09	Salpeter	UV+IR/UV SED	1.01	1.23	(.7, .3, .7)	$z/K_s/M_{4.5}$	Red	BC03	D	0.02-2.5	P84/C00	No 4
S12	Chabrier	UV+IR	0.57	0.70	(.73, .26, .74)	K-band	Blue	PEGASE.2	? ^a	? ^a	C00	No 1
S13	Kroupa	FUV SED	0.62	0.98	(.7, .3, .7)	LIR	Red	BC03/P07	D	1	P84/C00/C00b	Yes 2
W12	Chabrier ^h	UV+IR	0.60 ^a	0.73	(.7, .3, .7)	UVJ	Red	BC03	D	1	C00	Yes 5
Z12(1)	Chabrier	H α	0.66	0.97	(.7, .3, .7)	H β/σ_{R23}^j	Red	BC03	D	? ^a	C00	Yes 1
Z12(2)	Chabrier	H β	0.59	0.87	(.7, .3, .7)	H β/σ_{R23}	Red	BC03	D	? ^a	C00	Yes 1
Z12(3)	Chabrier	H β	0.59	0.87	(.7, .3, .7)	$U - G - R$	Red	BC03	D	? ^a	C00	Yes 1

* A list of the assumptions used when deriving the MS. The labelling scheme for the papers are listed in Section 3. IMFs, SFR indicator, SFR ratios (to K98 and KE12), cosmology, SPS model, SFH type, and extinction curve are listed/calculated as described in Section 2. The red/blue selection labelling scheme, used to account for observational biases, is described in Section 2.2.4. Selection criteria are labelled as detailed in Section 3. Metallicities have been taken from the paper in question.

^aNot explicitly listed, although it is mentioned that multiple are used.

^bUV and IR components of the SFR are weighted according to observations by Reddy et al. (2012a).

^cMasses are derived assuming a Chabrier IMF, while SFRs are derived assuming a Salpeter IMF calibrated on K98.

^dAlso includes various other emission lines calibrated to H α , which is used as a proxy for unobscured star formation.

^e z is redshift here.

^fAll the templates in R08 are empirical, albeit regenerated to high resolution from SPS models assuming a given SFR and extinction.

^gP84 is listed for the *sBzK* sample, but the extinction laws/assumptions applied to the IR sample are not explicitly listed.

^hMasses are derived assuming a Chabrier IMF, while SFRs are derived assuming a Kroupa IMF calibrated on Franx et al. (2008).

ⁱ σ_{R23} is the error in the *R23* parameter, which is the ratio of the oxygen nebular emission ([OII] 3727 Å doublet and [OIII] 4959 Å, 5007 Å) to H β .

Table 2. MS Calibrations

Assumption	Type	Calibration
Assumed IMF	SM	Zahid et al. (2012)
$L-\psi$ relation	SFR	Kennicutt & Evans (2012)
SPS Model	SM	Magdis et al. (2010)
Assumed SFH	SM/SFR	None
Dust Attenuation	SFR	Reddy et al. (2012a)
Extinction Law	SFR	None
Emission Lines	SM	Stark et al. (2013)
Cosmology	SFR	Spergel et al. (2003)
Photo-z's	SM/SFR	None
SED Fitting Procedure	SM/SFR	None
Selection Methods	Slope	Red (see Section 2.2.4)
Observational Biases	Slope	None

*A list of the calibrations we choose to establish between MS relations. See Section 2 for more details.

Table 3. MS relationships

Paper	z_{med}	z_{range}	Δt (Gyr)	α	β	σ (dex)	σ_d	σ_t	$\log M$ range	Sample size	Survey	Area (deg ²)	Stacked?
E11	0.05	0.0-0.1 ^a	1.301	1	-9.60	.26	.26	.16	9.6-11.3	648	various ^a	38960 ^a	No
E07(1)	0.06	0.015-0.1	1.094	.77	-7.44	.25	.25	.15	9.1-11.2	19590	SDSS DR4	705	No
Z12(1)	0.07	0.04-0.1	0.758	.71 ± .01 ⁿ	-6.78 ± 0.1	.25	.25	.15	8.5-10.4	~20000	SDSS DR7	8200	No
O10	0.1	0.0-0.2	2.432	.77 ± .02	-7.88 ± .22	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	9.1-11.6 ^m	8400	SWIRE	11.33	Yes
C09(1)	0.11	.005-.22	2.570	.35 ± .09	-3.56 ± .87	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	9.0-12.0 ^m	~500000 ^z	SDSS DR4	4783	Yes
S07	0.11	0.005-0.22	2.570	.65	-6.33	.3	.29	.21	9-11.1	48295	GALEX+SDSS DR4	645	No
O10	0.25	0.2-0.3	0.986	.63 ± .03	-6.21 ± .33	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	9.8-11.7	10984	SWIRE	11.33	Yes
W12 ^c	0.25	0.0-0.5	5.040	.67	-6.36	.34	.30	.22	9.3-10.6	4512	NMBS	0.4	No
K11	0.3	0.2-0.4	1.850	.56 ± .03	-5.43 ± 0.33	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	8.8-11.1	3385	COSMOS	1.72	Yes
O10	0.35	0.3-0.4	0.864	.68 ± .04	-6.67 ± .44	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	9.9-11.7	10478	SWIRE	11.33	Yes
N07	0.45	0.2-0.7	3.869	0.67 ± 0.08	-6.19 ± .78	.35	.32	.24	10.0-11.0 ^m	2905	AFGIS	0.5-1	No
O10	0.45	0.4-0.5	0.758	.73 ± .05	-7.02 ± .55	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	10.3-11.7	16856	SWIRE	11.33	Yes
S09	0.45	0.3-0.6	2.292	.7 ± .14	-6.33 ± 1.54	.3 ^d	.29	.2	7.3-11.2	~2500 ^e	GOODS-MUSIC	.040	No
K11	0.5	0.4-0.6	1.428	.58 ± .03	-5.28 ± 0.33	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	8.9-11.1	4406	COSMOS	1.72	Yes
O10	0.55	0.5-0.6	0.669	.54 ± .05	-4.85 ± .55	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	10.5-11.6	14987	SWIRE	11.33	Yes
K11	0.7	0.6-0.8	1.117	.60 ± .03	-5.27 ± 0.33	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	9.1-11.1 ^m	7820	COSMOS	1.72	Yes
O10	0.7	0.6-0.8	1.118	.36 ± .06	-2.74 ± .66	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	10.5-11.6	16004	SWIRE	11.33	Yes
W12 ^c	0.75	0.5-1.0	2.675	.60	-5.20	.34	.32	.25	9.6-10.8	8491	NMBS	0.4	No
Z12(2)	0.785	0.75-0.82	0.353	.67 ± .02	-5.91 ± 0.2	.27	.27	.18	9.3-10.6	1348	DEEP2	2.8	No
S09	0.8	0.6-1.0	2.005	.73 ± .15	-6.44 ± 1.65	.3 ^d	.29	.21	7.8-11.4	~2500 ^e	GOODS-MUSIC	.040	No
C09(2)	0.875	.75-1.0	1.143	.13 ± .15	-0.46 ± 1.57	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	10.0-12.0	~3000	DEEP2+POWIR	1.6	Yes
K11	0.9	0.8-1.0	0.888	.62 ± .03	-5.30 ± 0.33	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	9.1-11.1	11164	COSMOS	1.72	Yes
S12	0.9	0.5-1.3	3.695	.74	-6.63	.28 ^f	.28	.2	9.7-11.2	543	GOODS-S	0.033 ^g	No
E07(2)	1.0	0.8-1.2	1.603	.90	-8.14	.3	.29	.21	9.1-11.1 ^m	~1200	GOODS	.088	No
K11	1.1	1.0-1.2	0.715	.54 ± .03	-4.32 ± 0.33	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	9.3-11.1	9655	COSMOS	1.72	Yes
S09	1.25	1.0-1.5	1.550	.65 ± .13	-5.48 ± 1.43	.3 ^d	.29	.21	8.2-11.4	~2500 ^e	GOODS-MUSIC	.040	No
W12 ^c	1.25	1.0-1.5	1.550	.54	-4.14	.34	.33	.27	10.1-10.9	5451	NMBS	0.4	No
K11	1.4	1.2-1.6	1.065	.70 ± .03	-5.82 ± 0.33	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	9.5-11.1	19009	COSMOS	1.72	Yes
K13	1.55	1.4-1.7	0.693	.81 ± .04	-6.85 ± .4	.22	.22	.09	10-11.3	271	COSMOS	2	No
W12 ^c	1.75	1.5-2.0	0.974	.47	-3.17	.34	.34	.27	10.4-11.1	3292	NMBS	0.4	No
K11	1.8	1.6-2.0	0.744	.59 ± .07	-4.39 ± 0.60	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	9.7-11.1	14935	COSMOS	1.72	Yes
D07	1.95	1.4-2.5	1.879	.90	-7.6	.23 ¹	.21	.08	9.5-11.1	1291	GOODS	0.033 ^g	No
P09	2.0	1.0-3.0	3.638	.95 ± .07	-8.30	0 ^b	0 ^b	0 ^b	10.1-11.2	11798	GOODS	0.9	Yes
R11	2.0	1.5-2.5	1.627	.79	-6.42	.24	.22	.11	9.4-11.9	698+19567	COSMOS+GOODS-S	1.73	No
S09	2.0	1.5-2.5	1.627	.85 ± .17	-7.24 ± 1.87	.3 ^d	.29	.21	8.7-11.5	~2500 ^e	GOODS-MUSIC	.040	No

Table 3—Continued

Paper	z_{med}	z_{range}	Δt (Gyr)	α	β	σ (dex)	σ_d	σ_t	$\log M$ range	Sample size	Survey	Area (deg ²)	Stacked?
Z12(3)	2.0	1.41-2.57	1.926	.46 ± .07	-2.99 ± 0.7	.24	.22 .10	9.1-10.7	87	Erb et al. (2006)	.5 ^k	No	
R12	2.05	1.5-2.6	1.732	.97 ± .05	-8.28 ± 1.28	.37	.36 .3	8.7-11.3	302	various ⁱ	.081 ⁱ	No ^j	
K11	2.25	2.0-2.5	0.653	.58 ± .05	-4.16 ± 0.55	0 ^b	0 ^b 0 ^b	9.8-11.2	12927	COSMOS	1.72	Yes	
W12 ^c	2.25	2.0-2.5	0.653	.41	-2.30	.34	.34 .27	10.7-11.3	1070	NMBS	0.4	No	
K11	2.75	2.5-3.0	0.461	.56 ± .15	-3.73 ± 1.66	0 ^b	0 ^b 0 ^b	10.1-11.2	COSMOS	1.72	Yes	No	
M10	3.0	2.8-3.2	0.314	.91	-7.38	.3 ^d	.3 .22	9.7-11.5	196	Magdis et al. (2008)	.296	No	
S13	3.5	3.0-4.0	.596	.69 ± .01	-5.40 ± .15	.28	.28 .19	9.5-11.2 ^m	3424	SPLASH	2	No	
L11	3.7	3.3-4.1	0.425	.9 ± .1	-7.52 ± 1.1	0 ^b	0 ^b 0 ^b	10.0-11.2	1913	NDWFS	5.3	Yes	
L12	3.9 ^h	3.4-4.4 ^h	.482	.96	-9.02	.3	.3 .22	8.7-10.9	2952	GOODS	.089	No	
L12	5.0 ^h	4.4-5.6 ^h	.350	.90	-7.86	.3	.3 .22	9.0-10.9	846	GOODS	.089	No	
S13	5.0	4.0-6.0	.599	.55 ± .02	-3.63 ± .19	.24	.24 .13	10.0-11.6 ^m	1044	SPLASH	2	No	

* A list of all the main properties from the MS relations included in this work. α and β are defined per equation 1. Δt (in Gyr) has been calculated using our concordance cosmology. σ_d (deconvolved scatter) and σ_t (“true” scatter) are calculated as outlined in Section 4.1.

^aE11 draw their local sample from a subsample of galaxies described in Section 3. These have redshift distributions of objects from $z \sim 0$ to $\sim 0.2, 0.1$, and 0.088 , respectively, and so we take the average redshift distribution presented to be $\lesssim .1$. The survey with the largest area is the GOALS survey ($|b| > 5$, or 38960 deg^2), which is the one we list here.

^bSFRs derived via stacked data, so no measure of dispersion available.

^cDerived using W12’s functional form, applied to the median redshift of each bin.

^dEstimated from their Figure 7 (M10) and their Figure 3 (S09) as raw numbers not provided. The authors in question have been contacted for more exact data.

^eS09 report a total sample of 10511 (2146 IR-detected), but do not report the breakdown in each of the respective redshift bins. However, in all cases there are more than enough points (both UV and UV+IR) to robustly fit the MS.

^fS12 fit their data with a redshift-dependent power-law as a way of deconvolving the observed scatter with the time bin, similar to what we have done here, and do not provide the raw fits to the data.

^gD07 report using a fraction of the GOODS-N and GOODS-S fields, but do not list an exact area; R11, which uses the same sample, reports the exact area of the field covered.

^hL12 do not provide the actual redshift distribution (derived photometrically) of the sample included in the fit, so we estimate the distribution based on Vanzella et al. (2009). L12 report a median redshift of ~ 3.7 and 5.1 , and based on Vanzella et al. (2009)’s Figure 6, we find this is reasonably consistent with the distribution of observed B - and V -drops. Based on this, we take the distribution observed there as representative of the full distribution, with a redshift range of 3.4 - 4.4 and 4.4 - 5.6 (both slightly more heavily weighted towards the lower end) for the lower and higher redshift sample, respectively. For consistency with other works (where we have picked the midpoint

of the distribution), we choose $z_{med} = 3.9$ and 5.0 . We find that the difference in time this would lead to is only ~ 100 Myr and 30 Myr, respectively, quite small compared to the observed rate of MS evolution, and thus shouldn't lead to any major errors.

ⁱR12 draw their sample from a number of fields detailed in their Table 1, the largest of which (Q1623) is listed.

^jWhile most of the data are not stacked, the lower mass bins, which could not be detected in MIPS 24μ (181 out of 302 objects), are stacked and included in the fit.

^kErb et al. (2006) reports using a subset of galaxies selected from Steidel et al. (2004), which contains 7 fields totalling $\sim .5$ deg².

^l0.16 dex inter-quartile scatter is equivalent to 0.23 dex 1-sigma scatter.

^mTurnoff masses observed for these data. See Table ??.

ⁿWe wish to note that the errors on α and β compensate each other. Thus, calculating the SFR of a $10^{11} M_{\odot}$ galaxy does not cause the errors on each variable to add in quadrature; rather, they subtract in quadrature, and the final error is simply the square root of the magnitude of the differences between them. This does mean for some relations that, due to rounding in shifting the centerpoints of the relationships from $10^X M_{\odot}$, that the errors will approximately cancel out at some characteristic mass. However, we note that in most cases the fits and errors were derived fitting a distribution, and thus really are related to the observed σ of the distribution. Thus, when calculating characteristic SFRs for these MS relations, the errors on the fits themselves in most cases are in fact unimportant; the true errors simply can be found by adding $\pm\sigma$ to the calculated values, and adding in the fitted uncertainties in quadrature simply inflates the errors. We have left the derived uncertainties in here for completeness.

Table 4. MS Corrections

Paper	C_M	C_ψ	C_C	C_S	C_E	C_L	C_A	C_{tot}
E11	+0.21	-0.06	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00 ^a	+0.00	+0.00	+0.15
E07(1)	+0.16	-0.14	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.02
Z12(1)	-0.02	+0.01	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	-0.01
O10	+0.20	-0.12	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.17
C09(1)	+0.00	+0.15	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.15
S07	-0.02	-0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	-0.11
O10	+0.16	-0.12	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.13
W12	-0.02	+0.14	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.12
K11	-0.02	+0.30	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	-0.11	+0.26
O10	+0.18	-0.12	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.15
N07	+0.00	+0.19	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.19
O10	+0.19	-0.12	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.16
S09	+0.15	-0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.06
K11	-0.02	+0.30	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	-0.18	+0.19
O10	+0.14	-0.12	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.11
K11	-0.02	+0.30	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	-0.23	+0.14
O10	+0.09	-0.12	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.06
W12	-0.02	+0.14	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.12
Z12(2)	-0.02	+0.06	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.04
S09	+0.15	-0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.06
C09(2)	+0.00	+0.15	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.15
K11	-0.02	+0.30	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	-0.28	+0.09
S12	-0.02	+0.15	+0.02	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.15
E07(2)	+0.19	-0.11	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.08
K11	-0.02	+0.30	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	-0.32	+0.05
S09	+0.14	-0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.05
W12	-0.02	+0.14	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.12
K11	-0.02	+0.30	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	-0.38	-0.01
K13	+0.17	-0.20	-0.04	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	-0.07
W12	-0.01	+0.14	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.13
K11	-0.02	+0.30	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	-0.45	-0.08
D07	+0.19	-0.11	+0.01	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09
P09	+0.20	+0.03	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.32
R11	+0.17	-0.11	+0.01	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.07
S09	+0.18	-0.09	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09
Z12(3)	-0.01	+0.06	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.05
R12	+0.20	-0.09	+0.00	-0.15	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	-0.04
K11	-0.02	+0.30	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	-0.51	-0.14
W12	-0.01	+0.14	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.13
K11	-0.02	+0.30	+0.00	+0.00	+0.09	+0.00	-0.57	-0.20
M10	-0.03	+0.08	+0.00	-0.14	+0.00	+0.05	+0.00	-0.04
S13	+0.00	+0.01	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.01
L11	-0.03	-0.20	+0.01	+0.00	+0.00	+0.05	+0.00	-0.17
L12	-0.03	+0.00	+0.01	-0.14	+0.72	+0.05	+0.00	+0.61
L12	-0.03	+0.00	+0.01	-0.14	+0.72	+0.14	+0.00	+0.70
S13	+0.00	+0.01	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.00	+0.01

Table 4—Continued

Paper	C_M	C_ψ	C_C	C_S	C_E	C_L	C_A	C_{tot}
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*Corrections to MS observations based on Table 2 and outlined in Section 2, in dex. Subscripts are as follows: M = mass, ψ = SFR, C = cosmology, S = SPSModel, E = Extinction, L = EmissionLines, and A = Additionalmiscellaneouscorrections.

^aAn extinction correction (for missing unobscured UV emission) is not taken into account for E11 because they’ve selected a sample of LIRGS, which are display much higher dust attenuation (and hence IR emission) than the typical MS galaxy.

Table 5. Calibrated MS relationships

Paper	z_{avg}	z_{min}	z_{max}	Δt (Gyr)	α	β	σ_t (dex)	log M range
E11	0.05	0.0	0.1	1.301	1	-9.45	.16	9.4-11.1
E07	0.06	0.015	0.1	1.094	.77	-7.42	.14	8.9-11.0
Z12	0.07	0.04	0.1	0.758	.71 ± .01	-6.79 ± 0.1	.15	8.5-10.4
O10	0.1	0.0	0.2	2.432	.77 ± .02	-7.71 ± .22	0	8.9-11.4
C09	0.11	.005	.22	2.570	.35 ± .09	-3.41 ± .87	0	9.0-12.0
S07	0.11	0.005	0.22	2.570	.65	-6.44	.21	9-11.1
O10	0.25	0.2	0.3	0.986	.63 ± .03	-6.08 ± .33	0	9.6-11.5
W12	0.25	0.0	0.5	5.040	.67	-6.24	.22	9.3-10.6
K11	0.3	0.2	0.4	1.850	.56 ± .03	-5.25 ± 0.33	0	8.8-11.1
O10	0.35	0.3	0.4	0.864	.68 ± .04	-6.52 ± .44	0	9.7-11.5
N07	0.45	0.2	0.7	3.869	0.67 ± 0.08	-6.00 ± .78	.24	10.0-11.0
O10	0.45	0.4	0.5	0.758	.73 ± .05	-6.86 ± .55	0	10.1-11.5
S09	0.45	0.3	0.6	2.292	.7 ± .14	-6.27 ± 1.54	.2	7.1-11.0
K11	0.5	0.4	0.6	1.118	.58 ± .03	-5.17 ± 0.33	0	8.9-11.1
O10	0.55	0.5	0.6	0.669	.54 ± .05	-4.74 ± .55	0	10.3-11.5
K11	0.7	0.6	0.8	1.427	.60 ± .03	-5.30 ± 0.33	0	9.1-11.1
O10	0.7	0.6	0.8	1.118	.36 ± .06	-2.68 ± .66	0	10.3-11.5
W12	0.75	0.5	1.0	2.675	.60	-5.08	.24	9.6-10.8
Z12	0.785	0.75	0.82	0.353	.67 ± .02	-5.87 ± 0.2	.18	9.3-10.6
S09	0.8	0.6	1.0	2.005	.73 ± .15	-6.38 ± 1.65	.21	7.6-11.2
C09	0.875	0.75	1.0	1.143	.13 ± .15	-0.31 ± 1.57	0	10.0-12.0
K11	0.9	0.8	1.0	0.888	.62 ± .03	-5.29 ± 0.33	0	9.1-11.1
S12	0.9	0.5	1.3	3.695	.74	-6.48	.20	9.7-11.2
E07	1	0.8	1.2	1.603	.90	-8.06	.21	8.9-10.9
K11	1.1	1.0	1.2	0.715	.54 ± .03	-4.35 ± 0.33	0	9.3-11.1
S09	1.25	1.0	1.5	1.550	.65 ± .13	-5.43 ± 1.43	.21	8.0-11.2
W12	1.25	1.0	1.5	1.550	.54	-4.02	.26	10.1-10.9
K11	1.4	1.2	1.6	1.065	.70 ± .03	-5.91 ± 0.33	0	9.5-11.1
K13	1.55	1.4	1.7	0.693	.81 ± .04	-6.92 ± .4	.09	9.8-11.1
W12	1.75	1.5	2.0	0.974	.47	-3.04	.27	10.4-11.1
K11	1.8	1.6	2.0	0.744	.59 ± .07	-4.55 ± 0.60	0	9.7-11.1
D07	1.95	1.4	2.5	1.879	.90	-7.51	.08	9.3-10.9
P09	2.0	1.0	3.0	3.638	.95 ± .07	-8.07 ± .01	0	9.9-11.0
R11	2.0	1.5	2.5	1.627	.79	-6.35	.11	9.2-11.7
S09	2.0	1.5	2.5	1.627	.85 ± .17	-7.15 ± 1.87	.21	8.5-11.3
Z12	2.0	1.4	2.57	1.926	.46 ± .07	-2.94 ± 0.7	.10	9.3-10.6
R12	2.05	1.5	2.6	1.732	.97 ± .05	-8.32 ± 1.28	.30	8.7-11.3
K11	2.25	2.0	2.5	0.653	.58 ± .05	-4.38 ± 0.55	0	9.8-11.2
W12	2.25	2.0	2.5	0.653	.41	-2.17	.27	10.7-11.3
K11	2.75	2.5	3.0	0.461	.56 ± .15	-4.01 ± 1.66	0	10.1-11.2
M10	3.0	2.8	3.2	0.314	.91	-7.42	.22	10.0-11.8

Table 5—Continued

Paper	z_{avg}	z_{min}	z_{max}	Δt (Gyr)	α	β	σ_t (dex)	$\log M$ range
S13	3.5	3.0	4.0	.596	$.69 \pm .01$	$-5.39 \pm .15$.19	9.5-11.2
L11	3.7	3.3	4.1	0.425	$.9 \pm .1$	-7.69 ± 1.1	0	9.9-11.1
L12	3.9	3.4	4.4	.482	.96	-8.41	.22	8.8-11.0
L12	5.0	4.4	5.6	.350	.90	-7.16	.22	9.1-11.0
S13	5.0	4.0	6.0	.599	$.55 \pm .02$	$-3.62 \pm .19$.13	10.0-11.6

Table 6. Best MS Fits (time)

Fit	Data	Selection	Stacked?	SFR	N_{\min}	N_{tot}	$\log M_*$	range	z	range	α_c	α_t	β_c	β_t	σ_i
1	Corr(E)	All	All	All	N/A	46(35)	8.5-11.5	0.05-3.0	0.67	-0.002	-4.78	-0.13	0.16-0.21-0		
2	Uncorr(E)	All	All	All	N/A	46(35)	8.5-11.5	0.05-3.0	0.67	-0.002	-4.78	-0.14	0.18-0.23-0		
3	Corr(M)	All	All	All	5	46(35)	8.5-11.5	0.05-3.0	0.89 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-0.034 ± 0.002 ± 0.003	-7.08 ± 0.14 ± 0.21	0.19 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	0.05-0.15-0		
4	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	5	46(35)	8.5-11.5	0.05-3.0	0.95 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-0.042 ± 0.002 ± 0.003	-7.65 ± 0.14 ± 0.17	0.27 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	0.06-0.18-0		
5	Corr(M)	All	All	All	10	46(35)	9.0-11.4	0.05-3.0	0.85 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	-0.027 ± 0.002 ± 0.004	-6.7 ± 0.18 ± 0.25	0.13 ± 0.03 ± 0.04	0.11-0.15-0		
6	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	10	46(35)	9.0-11.4	0.05-3.0	0.92 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	-0.036 ± 0.003 ± 0.004	-7.42 ± 0.16 ± 0.26	0.22 ± 0.03 ± 0.04	0.1-0.18-0		
7	Corr(M)	All	All	All	15	46(35)	9.2-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.83 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-0.024 ± 0.002 ± 0.004	-6.41 ± 0.15 ± 0.28	0.1 ± 0.02 ± 0.04	0.13-0.15-0		
8	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	15	46(35)	9.2-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.88 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	-0.031 ± 0.002 ± 0.005	-6.95 ± 0.16 ± 0.29	0.16 ± 0.03 ± 0.05	0.14-0.18-0		
9	Corr(M)	All	All	All	20	46(35)	9.4-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.79 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-0.018 ± 0.002 ± 0.005	-6.04 ± 0.1 ± 0.27	0.04 ± 0.02 ± 0.05	0.13-0.15-0		
10	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	20	46(35)	9.4-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.85 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-0.027 ± 0.002 ± 0.005	-6.65 ± 0.14 ± 0.28	0.12 ± 0.02 ± 0.05	0.15-0.18-0		
11	Corr(M)	All	All	All	25	46(35)	9.6-11.1	0.05-3.0	0.78 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-0.018 ± 0.002 ± 0.005	-5.99 ± 0.1 ± 0.25	0.04 ± 0.02 ± 0.05	0.14-0.15-0		
12	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	25	46(35)	9.6-11.1	0.05-3.0	0.84 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-0.027 ± 0.002 ± 0.005	-6.58 ± 0.15 ± 0.29	0.12 ± 0.02 ± 0.05	0.16-0.19-0		
13	Corr(M)	All	All	All	30	46(35)	9.8-11.1	0.05-3.0	0.79 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-0.017 ± 0.001 ± 0.004	-6.0 ± 0.11 ± 0.23	0.04 ± 0.02 ± 0.04	0.14-0.16-0		
14	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	30	46(35)	9.8-11.1	0.05-3.0	0.83 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	-0.025 ± 0.002 ± 0.004	-6.44 ± 0.16 ± 0.3	0.1 ± 0.02 ± 0.04	0.17-0.19-0		
15	Corr(M)	All	All	All	35	46(35)	10.1-11.0	0.05-3.0	0.78 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-0.018 ± 0.002 ± 0.003	-6.0 ± 0.14 ± 0.28	0.04 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	0.14-0.16-0		
16	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	35	46(35)	10.1-11.0	0.05-3.0	0.81 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	-0.023 ± 0.003 ± 0.004	-6.21 ± 0.19 ± 0.36	0.08 ± 0.03 ± 0.04	0.17-0.19-0		
17	Corr(E)	All	No	All	N/A	27(19)	8.5-11.3	0.05-3.0	0.7	0.004	-5.08	-0.17	0.16-0.2-0		
18	Uncorr(E)	All	No	All	N/A	27(19)	8.5-11.3	0.05-3.0	0.7	0.004	-5.12	-0.17	0.15-0.19-0		
19	Corr(M)	All	No	All	5	27(19)	8.5-11.3	0.05-3.0	0.89 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	-0.015 ± 0.004 ± 0.007	-7.15 ± 0.16 ± 0.25	0.03 ± 0.04 ± 0.06	0.04-0.14-0		
20	Uncorr(M)	All	No	All	5	27(19)	8.5-11.3	0.05-3.0	1.01 ± 0.04 ± 0.03	-0.048 ± 0.011 ± 0.011	-8.34 ± 0.37 ± 0.3	0.34 ± 0.11 ± 0.1	0.05-0.14-0		
21	Corr(M)	All	No	All	10	27(19)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.87 ± 0.02 ± 0.04	-0.013 ± 0.004 ± 0.008	-6.87 ± 0.21 ± 0.37	0.01 ± 0.04 ± 0.08	0.09-0.15-0		
22	Uncorr(M)	All	No	All	10	27(19)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.9 ± 0.02 ± 0.04	-0.018 ± 0.003 ± 0.009	-7.26 ± 0.19 ± 0.38	0.06 ± 0.03 ± 0.09	0.08-0.15-0		
23	Corr(M)	All	No	All	15	27(19)	9.4-11.0	0.05-3.0	0.79 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-0.003 ± 0.002 ± 0.006	-6.13 ± 0.13 ± 0.28	-0.09 ± 0.02 ± 0.06	0.14-0.15-0		
24	Uncorr(M)	All	No	All	15	27(19)	9.4-11.0	0.05-3.0	0.84 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-0.01 ± 0.002 ± 0.006	-6.65 ± 0.13 ± 0.3	-0.02 ± 0.02 ± 0.06	0.13-0.15-0		
25	Corr(M)	All	No	All	20	27(19)	9.8-10.9	0.05-3.0	0.82 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-0.007 ± 0.001 ± 0.003	-6.42 ± 0.13 ± 0.23	-0.05 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	0.14-0.15-0		
26	Uncorr(M)	All	No	All	20	27(19)	9.8-10.9	0.05-3.0	0.85 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-0.012 ± 0.002 ± 0.003	-6.8 ± 0.15 ± 0.23	-0.0 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	0.13-0.15-0		
27	Corr(E)	All	Yes	All	N/A	19(16)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	0.62	-0.006	-4.2	-0.11	0.06-0.12-0		
28	Uncorr(E)	All	Yes	All	N/A	19(16)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	0.62	-0.006	-4.11	-0.14	0.1-0.14-0		
29	Corr(M)	All	Yes	All	5	19(16)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	0.47 ± 0.05 ± 0.08	0.007 ± 0.005 ± 0.008	-2.7 ± 0.49 ± 0.78	-0.23 ± 0.05 ± 0.08	0.06-0.1-0		
30	Uncorr(M)	All	Yes	All	5	19(16)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	0.5 ± 0.06 ± 0.09	0.004 ± 0.006 ± 0.01	-2.98 ± 0.65 ± 0.93	-0.22 ± 0.07 ± 0.1	0.07-0.11-0		
31	Corr(M)	All	Yes	All	10	19(16)	9.8-11.2	0.1-2.75	0.56 ± 0.03 ± 0.05	-0.001 ± 0.003 ± 0.005	-3.6 ± 0.33 ± 0.49	-0.15 ± 0.03 ± 0.05	0.06-0.09-0		

Table 6—Continued

Fit	Data	Selection	Stacked?	SFR	N_{\min}	N_{tot}	$\log M_*$ range	z range	α_c	α_t	β_c	β_t	σ_i
32	Uncorr(M)	All	Yes	All	10	19(16)	9.8-11.2	0.1-2.75	$0.61 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.05$	$-0.005 \pm 0.003 \pm 0.005$	$-4.01 \pm 0.3 \pm 0.52$	$-0.13 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.05$	$0.07-0.1-0.0$
33	Corr(M)	All	Yes	All	15	19(16)	10.2-11.1	0.1-2.75	$0.62 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.05$	$-0.006 \pm 0.001 \pm 0.005$	$-4.2 \pm 0.06 \pm 0.54$	$-0.11 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.06$	$0.07-0.09-0.0$
34	Uncorr(M)	All	Yes	All	15	19(16)	10.2-11.1	0.1-2.75	$0.63 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.04$	$-0.006 \pm 0.001 \pm 0.004$	$-4.16 \pm 0.07 \pm 0.43$	$-0.13 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.05$	$0.1-0.11-0.0$
35	Corr(E)	Red	All	All	N/A	33(27)	8.5-11.5	0.07-2.75	0.53	0.009	-3.22	-0.25	$0.13-0.17-0.0$
36	Uncorr(E)	Red	All	All	N/A	33(27)	8.5-11.5	0.07-2.75	0.53	0.009	-3.21	-0.27	$0.15-0.19-0.0$
37	Corr(M)	Red	All	All	5	33(27)	8.5-11.5	0.07-2.75	$0.75 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.06$	$-0.02 \pm 0.004 \pm 0.006$	$-5.65 \pm 0.45 \pm 0.56$	$0.06 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.06$	$0.05-0.12-0.0$
38	Uncorr(M)	Red	All	All	5	33(27)	8.5-11.5	0.07-2.75	$0.8 \pm 0.05 \pm 0.06$	$-0.027 \pm 0.004 \pm 0.006$	$-6.19 \pm 0.48 \pm 0.58$	$0.12 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.06$	$0.05-0.16-0.0$
39	Corr(M)	Red	All	All	10	33(27)	9.1-11.3	0.07-2.75	$0.74 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$-0.019 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.003$	$-5.53 \pm 0.2 \pm 0.28$	$0.04 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$0.1-0.12-0.0$
40	Uncorr(M)	Red	All	All	10	33(27)	9.1-11.3	0.07-2.75	$0.8 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.03$	$-0.028 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.003$	$-6.13 \pm 0.27 \pm 0.34$	$0.12 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$0.13-0.15-0.0$
41	Corr(M)	Red	All	All	15	33(27)	9.4-11.2	0.07-2.75	$0.7 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.02$	$-0.016 \pm 0.001 \pm 0.002$	$-5.11 \pm 0.11 \pm 0.21$	$0.01 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.02$	$0.1-0.12-0.0$
42	Uncorr(M)	Red	All	All	15	33(27)	9.4-11.2	0.07-2.75	$0.76 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$-0.025 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.003$	$-5.71 \pm 0.2 \pm 0.26$	$0.09 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$0.13-0.15-0.0$
43	Corr(M)	Red	All	All	20	33(27)	9.7-11.1	0.07-2.75	$0.71 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.01$	$-0.016 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.002$	$-5.16 \pm 0.12 \pm 0.14$	$0.01 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.02$	$0.1-0.11-0.0$
44	Uncorr(M)	Red	All	All	20	33(27)	9.7-11.1	0.07-2.75	$0.75 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.02$	$-0.024 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.003$	$-5.6 \pm 0.19 \pm 0.25$	$0.08 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$0.13-0.15-0.0$
45	Corr(M)	Red	All	All	25	33(27)	10.1-11.0	0.07-2.75	$0.72 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$-0.02 \pm 0.004 \pm 0.005$	$-5.31 \pm 0.25 \pm 0.36$	$0.05 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.05$	$0.1-0.11-0.0$
46	Uncorr(M)	Red	All	All	25	33(27)	10.1-11.0	0.07-2.75	$0.73 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.04$	$-0.024 \pm 0.004 \pm 0.006$	$-5.38 \pm 0.3 \pm 0.47$	$0.08 \pm 0.05 \pm 0.06$	$0.13-0.15-0.0$
47	Corr(E)	Red	No	All	N/A	16(12)	8.5-11.2	0.07-2.25	0.52	0.016	-3.11	-0.32	$0.11-0.17-0.0$
48	Uncorr(E)	Red	No	All	N/A	16(12)	8.5-11.2	0.07-2.25	0.52	0.016	-3.25	-0.31	$0.11-0.16-0.0$
49	Corr(M)	Red	No	All	5	16(12)	8.5-11.2	0.07-2.25	$0.88 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.06$	$-0.024 \pm 0.005 \pm 0.032$	$-6.98 \pm 0.22 \pm 0.57$	$0.1 \pm 0.05 \pm 0.3$	$0.0-0.1-0.0$
50	Uncorr(M)	Red	No	All	5	16(12)	8.5-11.2	0.07-2.25	$0.87 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.05$	$-0.024 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.027$	$-6.96 \pm 0.21 \pm 0.49$	$0.11 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.25$	$0.01-0.09-0.0$
51	Corr(M)	Red	No	All	10	16(12)	9.4-11.0	0.07-2.25	$0.81 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.02$	$-0.018 \pm 0.003 \pm 0.003$	$-6.19 \pm 0.21 \pm 0.25$	$0.04 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.03$	$0.09-0.11-0.0$
52	Uncorr(M)	Red	No	All	10	16(12)	9.4-11.0	0.07-2.25	$0.77 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.02$	$-0.015 \pm 0.003 \pm 0.003$	$-5.94 \pm 0.18 \pm 0.25$	$0.02 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.03$	$0.08-0.11-0.0$
53	Corr(E)	Red	Yes	All	N/A	17(15)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	0.53	0.004	-3.28	-0.21	$0.06-0.11-0.0$
54	Uncorr(E)	Red	Yes	All	N/A	17(15)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	0.53	0.004	-3.11	-0.24	$0.09-0.12-0.0$
55	Corr(M)	Red	Yes	All	5	17(15)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	$0.43 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.07$	$0.011 \pm 0.004 \pm 0.007$	$-2.33 \pm 0.46 \pm 0.68$	$-0.27 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.07$	$0.06-0.09-0.0$
56	Uncorr(M)	Red	Yes	All	5	17(15)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	$0.5 \pm 0.06 \pm 0.09$	$0.004 \pm 0.006 \pm 0.009$	$-2.96 \pm 0.67 \pm 0.88$	$-0.23 \pm 0.07 \pm 0.09$	$0.06-0.1-0.0$
57	Corr(M)	Red	Yes	All	10	17(15)	9.8-11.1	0.1-2.75	$0.54 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.03$	$0.002 \pm 0.001 \pm 0.003$	$-3.41 \pm 0.15 \pm 0.28$	$-0.18 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$0.06-0.08-0.0$
58	Uncorr(M)	Red	Yes	All	10	17(15)	9.8-11.1	0.1-2.75	$0.56 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.04$	$-0.001 \pm 0.003 \pm 0.005$	$-3.49 \pm 0.3 \pm 0.44$	$-0.19 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.05$	$0.07-0.1-0.0$
59	Corr(E)	Blue	All	All	N/A	13(8)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.88	-0.001	-7.08	-0.09	$0.11-0.14-0.0$
60	Uncorr(E)	Blue	All	All	N/A	13(8)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.88	-0.001	-7.09	-0.1	$0.14-0.15-0.0$
61	Corr(M)	Blue	All	All	5	13(8)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	$0.92 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.15$	$-0.003 \pm 0.007 \pm 0.046$	$-7.45 \pm 0.26 \pm 1.55$	$-0.07 \pm 0.07 \pm 0.49$	$0.06-0.14-0.0$
62	Uncorr(M)	Blue	All	All	5	13(8)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	$0.99 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.07$	$-0.024 \pm 0.011 \pm 0.021$	$-8.16 \pm 0.42 \pm 0.74$	$0.12 \pm 0.12 \pm 0.2$	$0.06-0.15-0.0$

Table 6—Continued

Fit	Data	Selection	Stacked?	SFR	N_{\min}	N_{tot}	$\log M_*$ range	z range	α_c	α_t	β_c	β_t
63	Corr(M)	Blue	All	All	10	13(8)	9.9-11.0	0.05-3.0	$0.87 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.04$	$-0.001 \pm 0.001 \pm 0.009$	$-7.01 \pm 0.11 \pm 0.38$	$-0.1 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.09$
64	Uncorr(M)	Blue	All	All	10	13(8)	9.9-11.0	0.05-3.0	$0.93 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.05$	$-0.006 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.013$	$-7.61 \pm 0.17 \pm 0.57$	$-0.06 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.13$
65	Corr(E)	Blue	No	All	N/A	11(7)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.87	-0.0	-6.95	-0.11
66	Uncorr(E)	Blue	No	All	N/A	11(7)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.87	-0.0	-6.89	-0.12
67	Corr(M)	Blue	No	All	5	11(7)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	$0.91 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.18$	$-0.004 \pm 0.006 \pm 0.056$	$-7.35 \pm 0.28 \pm 1.84$	$-0.07 \pm 0.06 \pm 0.58$
68	Uncorr(M)	Blue	No	All	5	11(7)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	$0.99 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.07$	$-0.024 \pm 0.011 \pm 0.02$	$-8.19 \pm 0.39 \pm 0.71$	$0.12 \pm 0.11 \pm 0.2$
69	Corr(M)	Blue	No	All	7	11(7)	9.3-11.0	0.05-3.0	$0.83 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.04$	$0.005 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.01$	$-6.57 \pm 0.12 \pm 0.38$	$-0.15 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.1$
70	Uncorr(M)	Blue	No	All	7	11(7)	9.3-11.0	0.05-3.0	$0.91 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.05$	$-0.005 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.014$	$-7.37 \pm 0.12 \pm 0.49$	$-0.07 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.13$
71	Corr(E)	All	All	Lines	N/A	7(4)	9.4-10.6	0.06-2.0	0.48	0.009	-2.98	-0.22
72	Uncorr(E)	All	All	Lines	N/A	7(4)	9.4-10.6	0.06-2.0	0.48	0.009	-3.0	-0.23
73	Corr(M)	All	All	Lines	5	7(4)	9.4-10.6	0.06-2.0	$0.34 \pm 0.05 \pm 0.07$	$0.02 \pm 0.005 \pm 0.008$	$-1.45 \pm 0.45 \pm 0.66$	$-0.34 \pm 0.05 \pm 0.08$
74	Uncorr(M)	All	All	Lines	5	7(4)	9.4-10.6	0.06-2.0	$0.38 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.06$	$0.017 \pm 0.004 \pm 0.008$	$-1.91 \pm 0.34 \pm 0.55$	$-0.3 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.08$
75	Corr(E)	All	All	UV	N/A	7(4)	9.3-11.0	1.0-3.0	0.86	0.004	-6.64	-0.21
76	Uncorr(E)	All	All	UV	N/A	7(4)	9.3-11.0	1.0-3.0	0.86	0.004	-6.4	-0.27
77	Corr(M)	All	All	UV	5	7(4)	9.3-11.0	1.0-3.0	$0.49 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.07$	$0.095 \pm 0.012 \pm 0.024$	$-2.78 \pm 0.42 \pm 0.69$	$-1.16 \pm 0.12 \pm 0.23$
78	Uncorr(M)	All	All	UV	5	7(4)	9.3-11.0	1.0-3.0	$0.89 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.06$	$-0.013 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.018$	$-6.64 \pm 0.3 \pm 0.6$	$-0.12 \pm 0.1 \pm 0.18$
79	Corr(E)	All	All	UV+IR	N/A	12(12)	8.5-11.2	0.25-2.25	0.65	0.002	-4.5	-0.18
80	Uncorr(E)	All	All	UV+IR	N/A	12(12)	8.5-11.2	0.25-2.25	0.65	0.002	-4.56	-0.19
81	Corr(M)	All	All	UV+IR	5	12(12)	8.5-11.2	0.25-2.25	$1.0 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.1$	$-0.042 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.029$	$-8.29 \pm 0.11 \pm 0.91$	$0.3 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.27$
82	Uncorr(M)	All	All	UV+IR	5	12(12)	8.5-11.2	0.25-2.25	$0.99 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.11$	$-0.044 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.035$	$-8.21 \pm 0.11 \pm 1.03$	$0.31 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.32$
83	Corr(M)	All	All	UV+IR	7	12(12)	9.4-11.2	0.25-2.25	$1.01 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.02$	$-0.042 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.005$	$-8.35 \pm 0.15 \pm 0.21$	$0.3 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.05$
84	Uncorr(M)	All	All	UV+IR	7	12(12)	9.4-11.2	0.25-2.25	$0.98 \pm 0.01 \pm 0.03$	$-0.043 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.006$	$-8.08 \pm 0.13 \pm 0.25$	$0.3 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.06$
85	Corr(E)	All	All	IR	N/A	7(5)	10.2-11.5	0.05-0.7	-0.15	0.084	2.91	-0.93
86	Uncorr(E)	All	All	IR	N/A	7(5)	10.2-11.5	0.05-0.7	-0.15	0.084	2.9	-0.95
87	Corr(M)	All	All	IR	5	7(5)	10.2-11.5	0.05-0.7	$0.93 \pm 0.18 \pm 0.36$	$-0.03 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.038$	$-8.59 \pm 1.94 \pm 3.9$	$0.28 \pm 0.21 \pm 0.41$
88	Uncorr(M)	All	All	IR	5	7(5)	10.2-11.5	0.05-0.7	$1.06 \pm 0.2 \pm 0.38$	$-0.044 \pm 0.022 \pm 0.039$	$-10.07 \pm 2.15 \pm 4.1$	$0.41 \pm 0.24 \pm 0.42$
89	Corr(E)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	N/A	19(17)	8.5-11.5	0.05-2.25	0.56	0.015	-3.63	-0.3
90	Uncorr(E)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	N/A	19(17)	8.5-11.5	0.05-2.25	0.56	0.015	-3.68	-0.31
91	Corr(M)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	5	19(17)	8.5-11.5	0.05-2.25	$0.88 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.06$	$-0.025 \pm 0.004 \pm 0.007$	$-7.04 \pm 0.2 \pm 0.56$	$0.12 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.07$
92	Uncorr(M)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	5	19(17)	8.5-11.5	0.05-2.25	$0.85 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.06$	$-0.025 \pm 0.004 \pm 0.007$	$-6.77 \pm 0.25 \pm 0.56$	$0.11 \pm 0.04 \pm 0.07$
93	Corr(M)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	10	19(17)	9.7-11.3	0.05-2.25	$0.89 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.07$	$-0.029 \pm 0.005 \pm 0.012$	$-7.21 \pm 0.29 \pm 0.71$	$0.16 \pm 0.06 \pm 0.12$

Table 6—Continued

Fit	Data	Selection	Stacked?	SFR	N_{\min}	N_{tot}	$\log M_*$ range	z range	α_c	α_t	β_c	β_t	
94	Uncorr(M)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	10	19(17)	9.7-11.3	0.05-2.25	$0.87 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.06$	$-0.026 \pm 0.005 \pm 0.011$	$-6.93 \pm 0.31 \pm 0.65$	$0.12 \pm 0.06 \pm 0.11$	0.14 ± 0.05
95	Corr(E)	All	All	Radio	N/A	10(10)	9.2-11.1	0.3-2.75	0.71	-0.015	-5.11	-0.0	0.05-C
96	Uncorr(E)	All	All	Radio	N/A	10(10)	9.2-11.1	0.3-2.75	0.71	-0.015	-4.94	-0.05	0.04-C
97	Corr(M)	All	All	Radio	5	10(10)	9.2-11.1	0.3-2.75	$0.73 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.04$	$-0.018 \pm 0.003 \pm 0.005$	$-5.34 \pm 0.21 \pm 0.4$	$0.04 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.05$	0.02 ± 0.02
98	Uncorr(M)	All	All	Radio	5	10(10)	9.2-11.1	0.3-2.75	$0.73 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$-0.019 \pm 0.002 \pm 0.003$	$-5.25 \pm 0.19 \pm 0.29$	$0.0 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.04$	0.02 ± 0.02

*Same as Table 3, with the corrections from Table 4 applied. Mass ranges have also been adjusted accordingly for IMF corrections.

Data are classified into corrected (Corr) and uncorrected (Uncorr) data, depending on whether we've applied our corrections from Table 4 or not. Data with a (M) have been bins of mass, taking into account mass ranges within each publication, while those with (E) have just fit all the data, extrapolating where there might not be explicit mass info (and thus just simply averaging over the reported slopes and normalizations). Red and blue selection methods are classified as per Section 2.2.4, and stacked and SFR sorting Table 3. N_{\min} is the minimum number of data points in a given mass bin required to include the bin in the fit, while N_{tot} is the total number of data points included from out criteria. The number in parentheses are excluding the first and last 2 Gyr of data, as classified by their median redshifts in Table 3. The $\log M_$ range is the number of mass bins in the fit. The z range is the total span in redshift, taken from the lower and upper bounds of the reported MS observations in Table 4. The first errors are the formal errors on the the form $\psi(M_*, t) = 10^{\beta(t)} \times M_*^{\alpha(t)}$, where $\alpha(t) = \alpha_t \times t + \alpha_c$ and $\beta(t) = \beta_t \times t + \beta_c$, with t measured in Gyr, as defined in Section 4. The first errors are the formal errors on the the second are the standard deviations around the best fits from 100 resamplings, with mass ranges for each study randomly adjusted by ± 0.2 dex each time, as detailed in Section interpublication scatter (σ_i) listed are the minimum, median, and maximum in each fit, respectively.

Table 7. Best MS Fits (redshift)

Fit	Data	Selection	Stacked?	SFR	N_{\min}	N_{tot}	$\log M_*$ range	z range	a_m	a_0	b_m	b_0	σ_i
1	Corr(E)	All	All	All	N/A	46(35)	8.5-11.5	0.05-3.0	0.09	1.99	0.64	-6.21	0.15-0.21-0.34
2	Uncorr(E)	All	All	All	N/A	46(35)	8.5-11.5	0.05-3.0	0.09	2.26	0.64	-6.36	0.15-0.2-0.33
3	Corr(M)	All	All	All	5	46(35)	8.5-11.5	0.05-3.0	0.55 ± 0.05 ± 0.07	-2.71 ± 0.49 ± 0.7	0.5 ± 0.02 ± 0.02	-4.9 ± 0.23 ± 0.23	0.09-0.16-0.29
4	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	5	46(35)	8.5-11.5	0.05-3.0	0.72 ± 0.05 ± 0.06	-4.27 ± 0.49 ± 0.59	0.45 ± 0.02 ± 0.02	-4.55 ± 0.22 ± 0.22	0.08-0.16-0.29
5	Corr(M)	All	All	All	10	46(35)	9.0-11.4	0.05-3.0	0.4 ± 0.05 ± 0.07	-1.22 ± 0.5 ± 0.68	0.55 ± 0.02 ± 0.02	-5.42 ± 0.2 ± 0.25	0.13-0.16-0.25
6	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	10	46(35)	9.0-11.4	0.05-3.0	0.58 ± 0.05 ± 0.06	-2.86 ± 0.47 ± 0.61	0.51 ± 0.02 ± 0.02	-5.1 ± 0.21 ± 0.23	0.11-0.16-0.25
7	Corr(M)	All	All	All	15	46(35)	9.2-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.31 ± 0.04 ± 0.07	-0.31 ± 0.44 ± 0.7	0.57 ± 0.02 ± 0.02	-5.61 ± 0.21 ± 0.24	0.13-0.15-0.24
8	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	15	46(35)	9.2-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.47 ± 0.04 ± 0.07	-1.68 ± 0.4 ± 0.7	0.53 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	-5.27 ± 0.19 ± 0.25	0.14-0.16-0.24
9	Corr(M)	All	All	All	20	46(35)	9.4-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.21 ± 0.03 ± 0.07	0.71 ± 0.35 ± 0.7	0.6 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	-5.83 ± 0.17 ± 0.26	0.13-0.15-0.24
10	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	20	46(35)	9.4-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.39 ± 0.03 ± 0.07	-0.84 ± 0.31 ± 0.69	0.54 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-5.44 ± 0.15 ± 0.26	0.14-0.15-0.25
11	Corr(M)	All	All	All	25	46(35)	9.6-11.1	0.05-3.0	0.19 ± 0.03 ± 0.07	0.94 ± 0.36 ± 0.67	0.6 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-5.88 ± 0.14 ± 0.26	0.13-0.15-0.22
12	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	25	46(35)	9.6-11.1	0.05-3.0	0.36 ± 0.03 ± 0.07	-0.61 ± 0.3 ± 0.68	0.55 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-5.48 ± 0.14 ± 0.28	0.14-0.15-0.22
13	Corr(M)	All	All	All	30	46(35)	9.8-11.1	0.05-3.0	0.2 ± 0.04 ± 0.08	0.76 ± 0.38 ± 0.79	0.61 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.91 ± 0.12 ± 0.23	0.13-0.15-0.2
14	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	30	46(35)	9.8-11.1	0.05-3.0	0.34 ± 0.03 ± 0.06	-0.39 ± 0.31 ± 0.58	0.56 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.6 ± 0.11 ± 0.2	0.15-0.15-0.2
15	Corr(M)	All	All	All	35	46(35)	10.1-11.0	0.05-3.0	0.25 ± 0.03 ± 0.07	0.22 ± 0.33 ± 0.77	0.6 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.8 ± 0.1 ± 0.18	0.14-0.15-0.2
16	Uncorr(M)	All	All	All	35	46(35)	10.1-11.0	0.05-3.0	0.34 ± 0.03 ± 0.05	-0.42 ± 0.35 ± 0.51	0.56 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.59 ± 0.13 ± 0.16	0.15-0.16-0.2
17	Corr(E)	All	No	All	N/A	27(19)	8.5-11.3	0.05-3.0	-0.03	2.96	0.73	-7.06	0.14-0.18-0.35
18	Uncorr(E)	All	No	All	N/A	27(19)	8.5-11.3	0.05-3.0	-0.03	3.06	0.73	-7.15	0.1-0.16-0.31
19	Corr(M)	All	No	All	5	27(19)	8.5-11.3	0.05-3.0	0.06 ± 0.09 ± 0.11	1.7 ± 0.94 ± 1.03	0.8 ± 0.04 ± 0.05	-7.67 ± 0.45 ± 0.45	0.04-0.13-0.19
20	Uncorr(M)	All	No	All	5	27(19)	8.5-11.3	0.05-3.0	0.47 ± 0.05 ± 0.09	-2.2 ± 0.54 ± 0.86	0.61 ± 0.02 ± 0.04	-5.98 ± 0.23 ± 0.43	0.06-0.11-0.18
21	Corr(M)	All	No	All	10	27(19)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.1 ± 0.05 ± 0.1	1.45 ± 0.54 ± 1.02	0.75 ± 0.02 ± 0.04	-7.23 ± 0.18 ± 0.42	0.1-0.13-0.19
22	Uncorr(M)	All	No	All	10	27(19)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.29 ± 0.05 ± 0.1	-0.33 ± 0.49 ± 1.01	0.69 ± 0.02 ± 0.04	-6.71 ± 0.17 ± 0.42	0.09-0.11-0.18
23	Corr(M)	All	No	All	15	27(19)	9.4-11.0	0.05-3.0	-0.05 ± 0.03 ± 0.08	3.0 ± 0.35 ± 0.79	0.78 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-7.53 ± 0.08 ± 0.32	0.12-0.14-0.18
24	Uncorr(M)	All	No	All	15	27(19)	9.4-11.0	0.05-3.0	0.14 ± 0.03 ± 0.07	1.24 ± 0.33 ± 0.7	0.72 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-7.05 ± 0.1 ± 0.29	0.09-0.11-0.16
25	Corr(M)	All	No	All	20	27(19)	9.8-10.9	0.05-3.0	-0.0 ± 0.05 ± 0.07	2.54 ± 0.49 ± 0.74	0.77 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-7.46 ± 0.09 ± 0.16	0.12-0.13-0.16
26	Uncorr(M)	All	No	All	20	27(19)	9.8-10.9	0.05-3.0	0.16 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	1.03 ± 0.23 ± 0.34	0.72 ± 0.01 ± 0.01	-7.01 ± 0.08 ± 0.15	0.09-0.1-0.13
27	Corr(E)	All	Yes	All	N/A	19(16)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	0.15	1.63	0.54	-5.41	0.1-0.14-0.23
28	Uncorr(E)	All	Yes	All	N/A	19(16)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	0.15	2.15	0.54	-5.64	0.09-0.14-0.23
29	Corr(M)	All	Yes	All	5	19(16)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	-0.49 ± 0.07 ± 0.13	8.38 ± 0.75 ± 1.3	0.61 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-6.13 ± 0.1 ± 0.18	0.09-0.12-0.22
30	Uncorr(M)	All	Yes	All	5	19(16)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	-0.48 ± 0.09 ± 0.13	8.8 ± 0.88 ± 1.29	0.61 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-6.4 ± 0.1 ± 0.21	0.07-0.1-0.24
31	Corr(M)	All	Yes	All	10	19(16)	9.8-11.2	0.1-2.75	-0.1 ± 0.05 ± 0.12	4.23 ± 0.51 ± 1.27	0.58 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.79 ± 0.11 ± 0.21	0.09-0.11-0.18

Table 7—Continued

Fit	Data	Selection	Stacked?	SFR	N_{\min}	N_{tot}	$\log M_*$ range	z range	a_m	a_0	b_m	b_0	σ_i
32	Uncorr(M)	All	Yes	All	10	19(16)	9.8-11.2	0.1-2.75	-0.07 ± 0.05 ± 0.12	4.48 ± 0.55 ± 1.26	0.58 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-6.01 ± 0.1 ± 0.22	0.07-0.1-0.18
33	Corr(M)	All	Yes	All	15	19(16)	10.2-11.1	0.1-2.75	0.01 ± 0.06 ± 0.12	3.11 ± 0.6 ± 1.28	0.57 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.72 ± 0.1 ± 0.23	0.1-0.11-0.15
34	Uncorr(M)	All	Yes	All	15	19(16)	10.2-11.1	0.1-2.75	0.12 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	2.48 ± 0.12 ± 0.3	0.56 ± 0.01 ± 0.01	-5.86 ± 0.07 ± 0.12	0.09-0.1-0.13
35	Corr(E)	Red	All	All	N/A	33(27)	8.5-11.5	0.07-2.75	-0.16	4.84	0.63	-6.27	0.13-0.17-0.229
36	Uncorr(E)	Red	All	All	N/A	33(27)	8.5-11.5	0.07-2.75	-0.16	5.13	0.63	-6.43	0.13-0.17-0.27
37	Corr(M)	Red	All	All	5	33(27)	8.5-11.5	0.07-2.75	0.33 ± 0.07 ± 0.11	-0.45 ± 0.72 ± 1.05	0.52 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.11 ± 0.12 ± 0.19	0.07-0.14-0.24
38	Uncorr(M)	Red	All	All	5	33(27)	8.5-11.5	0.07-2.75	0.49 ± 0.08 ± 0.11	-1.82 ± 0.79 ± 1.05	0.47 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-4.8 ± 0.12 ± 0.17	0.08-0.14-0.25
39	Corr(M)	Red	All	All	10	33(27)	9.1-11.3	0.07-2.75	0.21 ± 0.04 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.39 ± 0.62	0.55 ± 0.01 ± 0.01	-5.42 ± 0.11 ± 0.12	0.12-0.13-0.19
40	Uncorr(M)	Red	All	All	10	33(27)	9.1-11.3	0.07-2.75	0.39 ± 0.04 ± 0.06	-0.63 ± 0.42 ± 0.6	0.5 ± 0.01 ± 0.01	-5.1 ± 0.09 ± 0.11	0.12-0.15-0.2
41	Corr(M)	Red	All	All	15	33(27)	9.4-11.2	0.07-2.75	0.09 ± 0.03 ± 0.04	2.17 ± 0.32 ± 0.42	0.56 ± 0.01 ± 0.01	-5.54 ± 0.12 ± 0.12	0.12-0.13-0.18
42	Uncorr(M)	Red	All	All	15	33(27)	9.4-11.2	0.07-2.75	0.27 ± 0.02 ± 0.04	0.64 ± 0.24 ± 0.44	0.51 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.2 ± 0.09 ± 0.16	0.12-0.14-0.18
43	Corr(M)	Red	All	All	20	33(27)	9.7-11.1	0.07-2.75	0.08 ± 0.04 ± 0.04	2.27 ± 0.37 ± 0.46	0.57 ± 0.01 ± 0.01	-5.59 ± 0.14 ± 0.15	0.12-0.13-0.16
44	Uncorr(M)	Red	All	All	20	33(27)	9.7-11.1	0.07-2.75	0.23 ± 0.03 ± 0.04	1.06 ± 0.26 ± 0.41	0.52 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.24 ± 0.12 ± 0.18	0.12-0.14-0.16
45	Corr(M)	Red	All	All	25	33(27)	10.1-11.0	0.07-2.75	0.15 ± 0.06 ± 0.1	1.48 ± 0.61 ± 1.03	0.55 ± 0.02 ± 0.03	-5.41 ± 0.17 ± 0.26	0.12-0.13-0.14
46	Uncorr(M)	Red	All	All	25	33(27)	10.1-11.0	0.07-2.75	0.25 ± 0.05 ± 0.05	0.85 ± 0.56 ± 0.51	0.5 ± 0.02 ± 0.02	-5.11 ± 0.2 ± 0.2	0.12-0.13-0.15
47	Corr(E)	Red	No	All	N/A	16(12)	8.5-11.2	0.07-2.25	-0.34	6.63	0.72	-7.1	0.1-0.14-0.27
48	Uncorr(E)	Red	No	All	N/A	16(12)	8.5-11.2	0.07-2.25	-0.34	6.45	0.72	-7.12	0.07-0.12-0.25
49	Corr(M)	Red	No	All	5	16(12)	8.5-11.2	0.07-2.25	0.36 ± 0.08 ± 0.14	-0.81 ± 0.75 ± 1.35	0.62 ± 0.02 ± 0.06	-6.03 ± 0.17 ± 0.55	0.0-0.11-0.16
50	Uncorr(M)	Red	No	All	5	16(12)	8.5-11.2	0.07-2.25	0.35 ± 0.07 ± 0.16	-0.95 ± 0.65 ± 1.53	0.61 ± 0.02 ± 0.07	-5.9 ± 0.15 ± 0.68	0.02-0.09-0.16
51	Corr(M)	Red	No	All	10	16(12)	9.4-11.0	0.07-2.25	0.19 ± 0.04 ± 0.06	1.03 ± 0.39 ± 0.65	0.64 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-6.21 ± 0.14 ± 0.24	0.1-0.11-0.15
52	Uncorr(M)	Red	No	All	10	16(12)	9.4-11.0	0.07-2.25	0.13 ± 0.03 ± 0.05	1.42 ± 0.3 ± 0.5	0.63 ± 0.01 ± 0.01	-6.21 ± 0.09 ± 0.15	0.07-0.09-0.14
53	Corr(E)	Red	Yes	All	N/A	17(15)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	-0.05	3.58	0.57	-5.69	0.1-0.13-0.21
54	Uncorr(E)	Red	Yes	All	N/A	17(15)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	-0.05	4.29	0.57	-5.95	0.08-0.12-0.2
55	Corr(M)	Red	Yes	All	5	17(15)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	-0.53 ± 0.07 ± 0.1	8.78 ± 0.72 ± 1.09	0.61 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-6.17 ± 0.11 ± 0.17	0.09-0.11-0.22
56	Uncorr(M)	Red	Yes	All	5	17(15)	9.2-11.5	0.1-2.75	-0.48 ± 0.08 ± 0.11	8.82 ± 0.83 ± 1.16	0.62 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-6.43 ± 0.09 ± 0.17	0.07-0.09-0.23
57	Corr(M)	Red	Yes	All	10	17(15)	9.8-11.1	0.1-2.75	-0.21 ± 0.04 ± 0.09	5.37 ± 0.43 ± 0.93	0.6 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.97 ± 0.12 ± 0.18	0.1-0.11-0.17
58	Uncorr(M)	Red	Yes	All	10	17(15)	9.8-11.1	0.1-2.75	-0.17 ± 0.03 ± 0.07	5.6 ± 0.27 ± 0.69	0.59 ± 0.01 ± 0.01	-6.2 ± 0.07 ± 0.13	0.07-0.09-0.18
59	Corr(E)	Blue	All	All	N/A	13(8)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.06	1.57	0.85	-8.17	0.11-0.12-0.18
60	Uncorr(E)	Blue	All	All	N/A	13(8)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.06	1.8	0.85	-8.3	0.09-0.11-0.16
61	Corr(M)	Blue	All	All	5	13(8)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	-0.09 ± 0.06 ± 0.49	3.1 ± 0.61 ± 5.23	0.92 ± 0.02 ± 0.24	-8.87 ± 0.25 ± 2.53	0.0-0.12-0.16
62	Uncorr(M)	Blue	All	All	5	13(8)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.13 ± 0.05 ± 0.15	1.07 ± 0.56 ± 1.43	0.83 ± 0.02 ± 0.07	-8.04 ± 0.25 ± 0.66	0.05-0.1-0.15

Table 7—Continued

Fit	Data	Selection	Stacked?	SFR	N_{\min}	N_{tot}	$\log M_*$ range	z range	a_m	a_0	b_m	b_0	c
63	Corr(M)	Blue	All	All	10	13(8)	9.9-11.0	0.05-3.0	-0.1 ± 0.05 ± 0.12	3.26 ± 0.5 ± 1.27	0.88 ± 0.01 ± 0.05	-8.51 ± 0.11 ± 0.48	0.1-0.
64	Uncorr(M)	Blue	All	All	10	13(8)	9.9-11.0	0.05-3.0	0.04 ± 0.02 ± 0.1	1.96 ± 0.23 ± 1.08	0.85 ± 0.0 ± 0.05	-8.31 ± 0.04 ± 0.47	0.08-0
65	Corr(E)	Blue	No	All	N/A	11(7)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.03	1.8	0.85	-8.18	0.11-0
66	Uncorr(E)	Blue	No	All	N/A	11(7)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.03	2.15	0.85	-8.32	0.07-0
67	Corr(M)	Blue	No	All	5	11(7)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	-0.11 ± 0.06 ± 0.6	3.27 ± 0.57 ± 6.28	0.92 ± 0.02 ± 0.29	-8.85 ± 0.23 ± 3.05	0.0-0.
68	Uncorr(M)	Blue	No	All	5	11(7)	9.0-11.2	0.05-3.0	0.18 ± 0.05 ± 0.16	0.62 ± 0.51 ± 1.56	0.81 ± 0.02 ± 0.08	-7.91 ± 0.25 ± 0.75	0.05-0
69	Corr(M)	Blue	No	All	7	11(7)	9.3-11.0	0.05-3.0	-0.19 ± 0.04 ± 0.1	4.13 ± 0.43 ± 1.03	0.91 ± 0.02 ± 0.05	-8.79 ± 0.19 ± 0.48	0.1-0.
70	Uncorr(M)	Blue	No	All	7	11(7)	9.3-11.0	0.05-3.0	0.04 ± 0.03 ± 0.11	2.04 ± 0.29 ± 1.05	0.85 ± 0.01 ± 0.05	-8.31 ± 0.12 ± 0.5	0.07-0
71	Corr(E)	All	All	Lines	N/A	7(4)	9.4-10.6	0.06-2.0	-0.15	4.46	0.59	-5.77	0.11-0
72	Uncorr(E)	All	All	Lines	N/A	7(4)	9.4-10.6	0.06-2.0	-0.15	4.54	0.59	-5.83	0.12-0
73	Corr(M)	All	All	Lines	5	7(4)	9.4-10.6	0.06-2.0	-0.38 ± 0.09 ± 0.15	6.82 ± 0.92 ± 1.5	0.62 ± 0.01 ± 0.04	-6.05 ± 0.13 ± 0.37	0.07-0
74	Uncorr(M)	All	All	Lines	5	7(4)	9.4-10.6	0.06-2.0	-0.27 ± 0.07 ± 0.15	5.81 ± 0.69 ± 1.47	0.6 ± 0.01 ± 0.05	-5.99 ± 0.1 ± 0.49	0.1-0
75	Corr(E)	All	All	UV	N/A	7(4)	9.3-11.0	1.0-3.0	-0.0	2.0	0.88	-8.31	0.1-0.
76	Uncorr(E)	All	All	UV	N/A	7(4)	9.3-11.0	1.0-3.0	-0.0	2.95	0.88	8.75	0.02-0
77	Corr(M)	All	All	UV	5	7(4)	9.3-11.0	1.0-3.0	-1.65 ± 0.19 ± 0.3	19.32 ± 1.91 ± 2.99	1.57 ± 0.09 ± 0.16	-15.51 ± 0.9 ± 1.58	0.0-0.
78	Uncorr(M)	All	All	UV	5	7(4)	9.3-11.0	1.0-3.0	-0.52 ± 0.07 ± 0.1	8.5 ± 0.72 ± 1.08	1.07 ± 0.03 ± 0.04	-10.8 ± 0.28 ± 0.41	0.0-0.
79	Corr(E)	All	All	UV+IR	N/A	12(12)	8.5-11.2	0.25-2.25	-0.03	3.19	0.68	-6.56	0.06-0
80	Uncorr(E)	All	All	UV+IR	N/A	12(12)	8.5-11.2	0.25-2.25	-0.03	3.32	0.68	-6.7	0.08-0
81	Corr(M)	All	All	UV+IR	5	12(12)	8.5-11.2	0.25-2.25	0.73 ± 0.03 ± 0.31	-5.13 ± 0.35 ± 2.95	0.53 ± 0.01 ± 0.15	-4.95 ± 0.1 ± 1.39	0.04-0
82	Uncorr(M)	All	All	UV+IR	5	12(12)	8.5-11.2	0.25-2.25	0.77 ± 0.04 ± 0.38	-5.35 ± 0.4 ± 3.6	0.49 ± 0.01 ± 0.18	-4.72 ± 0.14 ± 1.73	0.04-0
83	Corr(M)	All	All	UV+IR	7	12(12)	9.4-11.2	0.25-2.25	0.64 ± 0.03 ± 0.04	-4.18 ± 0.34 ± 0.42	0.57 ± 0.01 ± 0.02	-5.42 ± 0.09 ± 0.17	0.04-0
84	Uncorr(M)	All	All	UV+IR	7	12(12)	9.4-11.2	0.25-2.25	0.62 ± 0.04 ± 0.07	-3.73 ± 0.39 ± 0.67	0.55 ± 0.01 ± 0.03	-5.35 ± 0.11 ± 0.27	0.07-0
85	Corr(E)	All	All	IR	N/A	7(5)	10.2-11.5	0.05-0.7	-2.28	25.52	0.96	-9.47	0.21-0
86	Uncorr(E)	All	All	IR	N/A	7(5)	10.2-11.5	0.05-0.7	-2.28	25.89	0.96	-9.65	0.23-0
87	Corr(M)	All	All	IR	5	7(5)	10.2-11.5	0.05-0.7	0.66 ± 0.51 ± 1.0	-6.25 ± 5.53 ± 10.65	0.51 ± 0.08 ± 0.15	-4.77 ± 0.9 ± 1.62	0.06-0
88	Uncorr(M)	All	All	IR	5	7(5)	10.2-11.5	0.05-0.7	0.96 ± 0.56 ± 1.03	-8.96 ± 6.04 ± 10.99	0.49 ± 0.09 ± 0.15	-4.67 ± 0.99 ± 1.6	0.04-0
89	Corr(E)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	N/A	19(17)	8.5-11.5	0.05-2.25	-0.22	5.34	0.72	-7.14	0.17-0
90	Uncorr(E)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	N/A	19(17)	8.5-11.5	0.05-2.25	-0.22	5.51	0.72	-7.29	0.17-0
91	Corr(M)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	5	19(17)	8.5-11.5	0.05-2.25	0.6 ± 0.07 ± 0.11	-3.35 ± 0.68 ± 1.1	0.54 ± 0.03 ± 0.04	-5.27 ± 0.26 ± 0.37	0.06-0
92	Uncorr(M)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	5	19(17)	8.5-11.5	0.05-2.25	0.63 ± 0.08 ± 0.12	-3.5 ± 0.8 ± 1.18	0.52 ± 0.03 ± 0.03	-5.18 ± 0.3 ± 0.36	0.05-0
93	Corr(M)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	10	19(17)	9.7-11.3	0.05-2.25	0.51 ± 0.07 ± 0.17	-2.57 ± 0.74 ± 1.75	0.56 ± 0.03 ± 0.06	-5.45 ± 0.34 ± 0.62	0.11-0

Table 7—Continued

Fit	Data	Selection	Stacked?	SFR	N_{\min}	N_{tot}	$\log M_*$ range	z range	a_m	a_0	b_m	b_0	σ_z
94	Uncorr(M)	All	All	UV+IR/IR	10	19(17)	9.7-11.3	0.05-2.25	$0.45 \pm 0.07 \pm 0.16$	$-1.64 \pm 0.79 \pm 1.62$	$0.56 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.06$	$-5.61 \pm 0.34 \pm 0.58$	$0.12-0.1$
95	Corr(E)	All	All	Radio	N/A	10(10)	9.2-11.1	0.3-2.75	0.23	0.33	0.55	-5.25	0.05-0.0
96	Uncorr(E)	All	All	Radio	N/A	10(10)	9.2-11.1	0.3-2.75	0.23	1.07	0.55	-5.57	0.06-0.0
97	Corr(M)	All	All	Radio	5	10(10)	9.2-11.1	0.3-2.75	$-0.19 \pm 0.07 \pm 0.12$	$4.65 \pm 0.73 \pm 1.26$	$0.64 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$-6.17 \pm 0.16 \pm 0.33$	$0.03-0.0$
98	Uncorr(M)	All	All	Radio	5	10(10)	9.2-11.1	0.3-2.75	$-0.31 \pm 0.09 \pm 0.12$	$6.73 \pm 0.92 \pm 1.23$	$0.65 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$-6.67 \pm 0.2 \pm 0.32$	$0.03-0.0$

Data are classified as Table 6, except the parameters listed are for a fitted function of the form $\psi(M_, z) = 10^{b(M_*)} \times (1+z)^{a(M_*)}$, where $a(M_*) = a_m \times \log M_* + b(M_*) = b_m \times \log M + b_0$.

Fig. 15.— Calculated $\log M$ tracks for galaxies with stellar masses of $10^{10}M_{\odot}$ at the present day, assuming direct SFR-to- M_* growth (black), a 0th order “return rate” (of stellar mass to gas mass) correction of 0.45 (blue), and a 1st order correction (accurate to within a few percent) to account for mass loss from older stars (red), and that they follow the MS at all times. Both feedback prescriptions are taken from Leitner & Kravtsov (2011) and Leitner (2012) and assume a Chabrier IMF (functionally equivalent to a Kroupa IMF). Initial seed masses of 10^7M_{\odot} are assumed, as below this mass dwarf galaxies with extremely low metallicities might display significant deviation from typical MS behavior. As mass growth is extremely rapid at small masses, however, the plotted formation times and ages are only weakly a function of mass.

Fig. 16.— Same as Figure 15, but for $\log \psi$. Dashed lines indicate the return rate for the given correction as a function of time, and dashed-dotted lines indicate the mass growth the galaxy over the same period. Feedback is necessary not only to push back galaxy formation times, but also on average increases the galaxy’s peak SFR, with massive galaxies at a given redshift galaxies contributing much more to the cSFR than lower mass ones.

Fig. 17.— Same as Figure 16, but for ψ . The magnitude of the peak for galaxies including 1st-order feedback can more clearly be seen.

Fig. 18.— Same as Figure 16, but for the sSFR. As can be clearly seen, the sSFR (i.e. the SFR efficiency of galaxies at a given mass) decreases over time to the present day values. Feedback leads to a more gradual, linear decline in the sSFR (in log space) compared to the no-feedback track.

Fig. 19.— Same as Figures 15 and 16, but for $M_*(t)$ as a portion of $M_*(t = t_0)$. The behavior of the normalized mass growth rate and the SFR is also overplotted, showing that feedback is necessary to shift the peak SFRs to earlier epochs, as indicated by observations over the past two decades.

Fig. 20.— As Figure 19, except for a $\log M_*(t = t_0) = 11$ galaxy. The SFR peaks earlier than for a $\log M_*(t = t_0) = 10$ galaxy, at around $z \sim 1$ ($t \sim 5.75$) rather than $0.5 < z < 1$ ($8.4 > t > 5.75$). If we allow for even higher initial formation masses and earlier formation times (galaxies with SMs of at least $10^{11}M_\odot$ are observed at $z > 4$), we find that the SFR for a $\log M_*(t = t_0) = 12 - 12.5$ galaxy peaks at $2 < z < 3$ ($3.2 > t > 2.1$). Taking these together along with their approximate observed number densities at a given redshift leads to good qualitative agreement with the observed evolution in the cSFR (Hopkins & Beacom 2006).

Fig. 21.— $\log M_*$ evolution from MSI tracks assuming 1st-order feedback for MS galaxies following the same evolutionary tracks (with the leading, green, and lagging, red, groups following the same evolution as the blue) but that have “formed” (i.e. entered the MS) ~ 1.4 Gyr apart (i.e. are evolving synchronously 1.4 Gyr apart), which evolve until $z = 0.5$.

Fig. 22.— As Figure 21, but for $\log \psi$.

Fig. 23.— As Figure 21, but for the evolving $\log M_*$ – $\log \psi$ relation.

Fig. 24.— As Figure 23, but here we’ve drawn the appropriate MS relations that would be observed for each group of galaxies if they are observed at $z \sim 0.5$. A slope of unity (purple dashed line), is shown for contrast.

Fig. 25.— The observed scatter (in dex) from the MS (as visible from ??) as a function of the separation time, measured at three fiducial masses of $\log M_* = 9, 10,$ and 11 . Not only does the observed scatter increase linearly as a function of separation time, but the observed scatter is also mass-dependent, with larger masses displaying more scatter than smaller masses. The most likely true scatter about the MS (~ 0.2 dex) is marked with a dashed purple line, and the corresponding separation time (~ 1.4 Gyr) is marked with a dashed green line.

Fig. 26.— The scatter observed for the same fiducial masses chosen in Figure 25 as a function of time. In agreement with observed data, a constant formation spread/offset but synchronous evolution of 1.4 Gyr reproduces well the observed true scatter about the MS, and also remains constant over time.